

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v1.0

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Lead Beneficiary	ATOS		
Responsible Author	Guillermo Gomez, Elisa Jimeno		
Contributors	Muhammad Mahtab (TTU), George Agapiou (WINGS), Luis Sanabria-Russo (CTTC), Christos Skoufis (EBOS), Anastasios Drosou (CERTH), Kostas Ramantas (IQU), Natalia Vassileva (CTTC), Johan Scholliers (VTT), Maria Efthymiopoulou (IQU), Yannick Le Moullec (TTU)		
Peer reviewer	EBOS (Philippou Philippou); TTU (Margus Rohtla);		
Additional review on WP1-Wp4 deliverables	Artūrs Nikolājevs (LMT); Priit Roosipuu (TTU); Kati Kõrbe (EEE); Kristjan Kuhl (EEE); Annarita Leserri (ENIDE)		

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Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	11
2	Introduction.....	13
2.1	Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs.....	13
2.2	Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	14
2.3	Linkage to other Project Outputs	15
3	5G-ROUTES Integration Methodology	18
3.1	Integration Objectives	18
3.2	Integration Process Steps	19
3.3	Integration Timeline	19
4	5G-ROUTES Software Contribution Guidelines	21
4.1	Introduction.....	21
4.1.1	Software Version Control	21
4.1.2	Software Management Platform.....	22
4.2	5G-ROUTES Git Platform.....	23
4.2.1	Reporting and Documentation	24
4.2.2	Artefact Registry	25
4.2.3	DevOps.....	25
4.2.4	Branch naming.....	27
4.2.5	Merge Requests.....	27
4.2.6	CICD Framework.....	30
4.3	5G-ROUTES CICD.....	31
5	5G-ROUTES Testing Guidelines.....	33
5.1	Introduction.....	33
5.1.1	Test Driven Development.....	33
5.2	Enablers and Tenant Web Portal Testing	35
5.2.1	Unit Test	35
5.2.2	Functional Tests.....	35
5.3	5G-ROUTES Platform Testing.....	35
5.3.1	Integration Tests.....	36
6	5G-ROUTES Platform Cloud Deployment Guidelines	37
6.1	Introduction.....	37
6.1.1	Network Function Virtualization	37
6.1.2	Containers.....	38
6.1.3	Kubernetes.....	39
6.1.4	Cloud-Native Infrastructure Service	39
6.2	5G-ROUTES Platform Deployment	39
6.2.1	Deployment Strategy and Requirements	40
6.2.2	Deployment Timeline	43
6.3	Testbed environment	44
6.3.1	CTTC testbed.....	45
6.3.2	TTU testbed	46
6.3.3	VTT testbed.....	46
7	5G-ROUTES Enablers and Tenant Web Portal.....	47
7.1	AI Assisted Cross-domain MEC and Integration Fabric for CAM Services.....	48
7.1.1	Integration Fabric	49
7.1.2	CAM Repository.....	50
7.1.3	Assisted Handover in Cross-domain.....	52
7.1.4	Resource Allocation and Positioning of V2X relate NFs	52

7.1.5	Low-latency Cross-border Synchronisation Mechanism for Seamless CAM Service Delivery	53
7.1.6	V2X Routing using MEC	55
7.2	End-to-End Slicing Optimization and Innovative Spectrum Usage for CAM Services	57
7.2.1	Network Slicing for CAM Services	57
7.2.2	Slice Negotiator	58
7.3	AI-based Positioning Enhancements for V2X	59
7.3.1	5G Localization for VRU Protection	59
7.3.2	5G Network-based Positioning and 5G Integrated Hybrid Positioning	61
7.4	Tenant Web Portal.....	63
7.4.1	Artefacts	64
7.4.2	Tenant Web Portal Interfaces.....	65
7.4.3	Development Timeline	65
8	5G-ROUTES Platform	66
8.1	Core Cloud Enablers	67
8.2	Edge Cloud Enablers	69
9	Conclusions.....	70
10	References.....	71

List of Figures

Figure 1	View of the relation between D2.9 and others 5G-ROUTES project deliverables	16
Figure 2	T2.5 internal milestones	19
Figure 3	Comparison of Git management platforms [14]	22
Figure 4	GitLab vs GitHub free functionalities [13]	24
Figure 5	5G-ROUTES GitLab Group named “5G-PPP-5G-ROUTES”	24
Figure 6	Workflow of Software Issues.....	25
Figure 7	Gitflow reference graph	27
Figure 8	Squash-based merge request commits	28
Figure 9	GitLab submit Merge Request UI	28
Figure 10	GitLab Merge Request UI.....	29
Figure 11	Gitlab CICD communication call flow	31
Figure 12	5G-ROUTES CICD implementation.....	31
Figure 13	Enablers GitFlow with CICD trigger events.....	32
Figure 14	Test-Driven development.....	34
Figure 15	Deployment History of Setups [31]	38
Figure 16	5G-ROUTES Project Architecture [18]	39
Figure 17	5G-ROUTES deployment strategy in T2.5.....	41
Figure 18	OSM alignment with ETSI specifications [30]	42
Figure 19	OSM North Bound API	42

Figure 20 Simple NSD (left) with a single CNF (right)	43
Figure 21 Enablers Timeline synchronization with Testbeds	44
Figure 22 Integration Fabric interfaces	50
Figure 23 CAM Repository interfaces.....	51
Figure 24 Low-latency cross-border Synchronization for CAM Services Enabler.....	55
Figure 25 V2X communication architecture using MQTT/AMQP – based routing application.....	56
Figure 26 VRU Localization Closed Loop	60
Figure 27 VRU Localization interfaces	61
Figure 28. Approach for improving localization accuracy.	62
Figure 29 TWP Visualization Dashboard Components and Flow of Information.....	64
Figure 30 5G-ROUTES Platform overview.....	67
Figure 31 5G-ROUTES Core Cloud	68
Figure 32 5G-ROUTES Edge Cloud	69

List of Tables

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.....	13
Table 2 D2.9 Contributions and Values of linkage.....	16
Table 3 Contributions of D2.9 from and to the rest of the deliverables.	17
Table 4 T2.5 activities timeline.....	20
Table 5 Summary of Technological Enablers.....	47
Table 6 Integration Fabric Task Activities Planning.....	50
Table 7 CAM Repository Task Activities Planning.....	51
Table 8 Assisted handover Task Activities Planning.....	52
Table 9: Resource allocation and positioning of V2X related NFs enabler Task Activities Planning.....	53
Table 10 Low-latency cross-border synchronisation mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery task activity planning.....	55
Table 11 V2X routing using MEC Task Activities Planning.....	57
Table 12 Network slicing for CAM solution: development plan.....	58
Table 13 Slice negotiator Task Activities Planning	59
Table 14 5G localization for VRU protection enabler Task Activities Planning	61
Table 15 5G network-based positioning and 5G integrated hybrid positioning task activities planning	63
Table 16 Tenant Web Portal Development Timeline	65
Table 17 Enablers mapping to UCs in 5G-ROUTES	66

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	Fifth Generation
5G NR	5G New Radio
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interfaces
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
CICD	Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery
CNF	Container Network Functions // Cloud-native Network Functions
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CPS	Collective Perception System
CSMF	Communication Service Management Function
DevOps	Development & Operations
DL	Deep Learning
DRL	Deep Reinforce Learning
E2E	End-to-End
EO	Ericsson Orchestrator
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GA	Grant Agreement
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GPS	Global Positioning System
HW	Hardware
HO	Hand-Over
IaC	Infrastructure as code
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
K8S	Kubernetes
MANO	Management and orchestration

MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MR	Merge Request
MNO	Mobile Network operator
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
NEST	NEtwork Slice Type
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVI	Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure
NS(D)	Network Service (Descriptor)
NSMF	Network Slice Management Function
NSSMF	Network Slice Subnet Management Function
NUC	Next Unit of Computing
OAI	OpenAiInterface
OBU	On-Board Unit
OSM	Open-Source MANO
OSS/BSS	Operations support systems/Business support systems
OOP	Object Oriented Programming
SaaS	Software as a Service
SW	Software
SDR	Software Define Radio
RSU	Road-side Unit
TDD	Test Driven Development
TOF	Time Of Flight
TWP	Tenant Web Portal
UC	Use Case
UWB	ultra-wideband
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VM	Virtual Machine
VNF(D)	Virtual Network Function (Descriptor)
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager

D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological Enablers for CAM v1.0

WIM	WAN Infrastructure Manager
WP	Work Package
ZSM	Zero touch network & Service Management

1 Executive Summary

Being 5G-ROUTES a Phase-3 5G-PPP project, one of its objectives is to provide a practical and novel 5G Platform specialized in the field of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) services with emphasis on cross-domain scenarios. Such Platform will serve Use Cases (UCs) as the gate to an underlying 5G infrastructure, which will be first tested in a controlled laboratory prior to the actual production-grade tests in a field trial. The 5G-ROUTES Platform is a multi-cloud system (core and edge) built as the combination of innovative technological enablers developed within the project to comply with the needs of CAM UCs. Therefore, enablers are to be understood in this project as pieces of software that facilitate an enhancement or new functionality over a 5G Infrastructure. Each enabler will offer and/or produce functionalities from the 5G-ROUTES Platform to the UC Services. The 5G-ROUTES Platform is the output of Work Package (WP) 2 to successive WPs. WP3 will ensure that enablers provide compatible interfaces with the field trial 5G infrastructure and orchestrator specifications so that UCs are able to proceed with their testing cycles in commercial field trials environments.

T2.5 aims at the integration and deployment as well as the validation and testing of a 5G Platform that coordinates the interaction between the set of enablers developed in WP2. It will ensure that enablers are developed to a high standard and that they can all be integrated as a single 5G-ROUTES Platform deployed in a 5G-compatible approach within one of the available testbeds of the project. Functionality of enablers in isolation as well as deployment and connectivity among enablers will be tested in a continuous and automatized process. This document will set the grounds for a seamless integration of the work done by different partners developing the 5G-ROUTES technological enablers, in a way that will make it possible to start the integration of enablers into the Platform as soon as possible and have it work seamlessly for all teams for the duration of their development. By endorsing the different guidelines and procedures that this document holds, WP2 will be able to prove that:

- Enablers offer some level of unit and functional testing which in turn relates to the quality of the code, the coverage of testing and the correctness of the most critical features offered.
- Enablers offer a virtualization mechanism compatible with a 5G deployment.
- The 5G-ROUTES Platform is offered as a 5G-compatible deployment that is tested to work with a 5G Orchestrator. In particular, Containerized Network Functions (CNF) deployed via ETSI Open-Source MANO (OSM) in a testbed environment.
- The 5G-ROUTES Platform tests that enablers deployed have network connectivity among each other and that they are deployed to the desired location (core and edge clouds).
- The 5G-ROUTES Platform tests that the interfaces of enablers are aligned and that the main functionalities offered to UCs are tested in a dry-run configuration.

WP3 will continuously provide insight on the 5G infrastructure available in testbeds and field trials so that enablers can be configured to interface with those systems. The resulting Platform will be afterwards integrated into field infrastructure within WP3 as well, to execute localized and extended trials of the UCs. This document includes a summary of the latest interfaces and artefacts produced by enablers which are used to offer an initial integration and deployment strategy that will be later advanced by T3.3 to adapt the 5G-ROUTES Platform to the field trials.

A series of common guidelines will be defined along with a number of resources that will be made available for the teams to use. The most immediate achievement of this document is a collection of development and testing guidelines that will drive the upcoming development of the enablers. The contributions of partners towards enablers will follow an automated validation framework in the form of continuous integration and continuous delivery (CICD) pipelines. Firstly, covering the isolated development and testing, and secondly in a common environment where their communication with other enablers. New features and improvements originated from the interaction between WP2, WP3 and WP4 will be identified and requested to the corresponding partner to include into their enabler. Thus, enabling an early iteration of an enabler's release to facilitate that UCs are able to meet the KPIs detailed in WP1.

Upcoming deliverable from T2.5 (D2.10) due to M36 of the project will report on the final 5G-ROUTES Platform containing a full description of the interactions and capabilities that were tested. The final deployment strategy, configuration and lessons learnt. Enablers will provide the final set of functionalities offered to the Platform and UCs along with the improvements carried out during the different testing cycles in the context of WP2, WP3 and WP4.

2 Introduction

The content of this deliverable describes the work done in T2.5 until M16 in the project. T2.5 is the last of the activities planned for WP2 in the 5G-ROUTES schedule. This has been set up so that previous tasks could provide enough input for T2.5 to form an aggregated picture of the outcomes of WP2. The main result of the WP2 shall be a 5G Platform in lab environment which leverages the set of enablers developed in WP2 tasks (from T2.1 to T2.4). This deliverable is therefore planned to include an initial version of the technical information required by successive WPs to understand how the 5G-ROUTES Platform and the technological enablers fit together. It is also planned to work as a WP2 handbook for developers where they can find the guidelines and methodologies for development, integration and testing within the project.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this Chapter is to map 5G-ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal deliverable and task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v1.0	Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v1.0: Initial (v1.0) version of report	Chapter 2, Chapter 3, Chapter 4, Chapter 5, Chapter 6, Chapter 7, Chapter 8	Chapter 3 shows overall integration methodology, the work planned, activities undertaken and timeline for the integration of technological enablers and the 5G-ROUTES Platform. Chapter 4, 5 and 6 include a collection of guidelines and methodologies that will be used for the development, integration and testing of enablers. Chapter 7 collects the required information about the different enablers and about the Tenant Web Portal to carry out an integration. Chapter 8 provides an update of the 5G-ROUTES Platform taking into account the enablers and guidelines related to deployment and integration.
TASKS			
Task T2.5 - Integration and testing of	The objective of this task is to perform the integration, configuration and evaluation of the technological Enablers, to	Chapter 4, Chapter 5, Chapter 6	Several technologies and methodologies are presented to drive the development and deployment of the different enablers to create a uniform, continuous testing process so that they can prove

<p>technological Enablers</p>	<p>ensure they are compliant with the requirements and specifications specified in D1.1.</p>		<p>their compliance with the requirements from D1.1.</p>
	<p>Perform dry-run interworking tests to verify proper operation, functionality and interoperability prior to live deployment in large-scale field trials. In this task, an evaluation of the performance capabilities of all technological enablers and the Tenant Web Portal will be conducted after every testing cycle, based on the outcomes of deliverable D4.3 to perform potential incremental improvements in their functionalities. In particular, to ensure the correctness of the ML algorithms at the positioning, MEC, network slicing and spectrum allocation subsystems in an integrated way, testing their reaction to changes in traffic and mobility patterns and simulating extreme events.</p>	<p>Chapter 4, Chapter 5, Chapter 6, Chapter 7, Chapter 8</p>	<p>Chapter 4 details how the integration and testing will be carried out using a Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery (CICD) framework.</p> <p>Chapter 5 covers a description of the suite of tests that should be provided from the enabler’s developer teams as well as from the integration developers team to ensure the reliability of the components in isolation and in an integrated testing environment (dry-run).</p> <p>Chapter 6 gives an overview on the virtualization technology and its usage inside the project as to prepare an integrated environment where all enablers can be deployed and interconnected in the form of what is defined as the 5G-ROUTES Platform.</p> <p>Chapter 7 collects the available technical description from each enabler and from the Tenant Web Portal related to their implementation and thus how they can be integrated to the different testbeds and further test their connectivity.</p> <p>Chapter 8 takes the enablers and presents an updated 5G-ROUTES Platform overview that will allow integration testing and the baseline configuration for WP3 to further integrate with the infrastructure.</p>

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The current document is structured in several Chapters that describe the agreed methodology and tools to perform the integration, configuration and evaluation of the enablers developed in WP2; and served as deployment path for the validation on WP3. The deliverable is organized as follow:

- Chapter 1 contains the executive summary of the deliverable
- Chapter 2 (this Chapter) highlights task commitment mapping on the work performed and disclose the outputs of the activity.

- Chapter 3 details the scope and objectives of T2.5 which conform the methodology proposed. It also explains what activities have been identified within T2.5, their mapping to the different Chapters on the document and a timeline showing whether they are finished or not.
- Chapter 4 explores the software industry and explain how DevOps will be used in the project. It offers a handbook of tools that are been made available to dev teams to align their contributions at the same time that stablishes an automated validation framework based on CICD to continuously integrate and test enablers.
- Chapter 5 moves into the specific testing guidelines that will contribute toward the validation of the objectives of the integration task. It initially focuses on the technological enablers in isolation and then in an integrated environment that has been defined as the 5G-ROUTES Platform. The integration of the enablers will be based on different types of testing to verify the correct functioning of the developed features, and the compliance with the overall architecture. Platform level testing is also introduced as part of the test suite description.
- Chapter 6 presents the deployment and integration strategy that will be configured in the context of T2.5. It shows how it has been designed to be aligned with the capabilities of the different testbeds as well as with the initial information obtained from field trials while leveraging a CICD pipeline for the validation of the integration of enablers. A first planning of the releases of the enablers and the 5G-ROUTES Platform is also depicted along with the target testbed environment that each enabler will need.
- Chapter 7 classifies and identifies the enablers that will be produced during the execution of WP2. Their description include the interfaces and artefacts required to deploy each of them which helped designing the deployment strategy.
- Chapter 8 shows an updated overview of the 5G-ROUTES Platform as the outcome of WP2, considering the role of each enabler and explains the different connectivity links that will target of validation as part of the integration testing.
- And finally, Chapter 9 concludes the result of the document with the wraps up and provides insight on the planned future work.

2.3 Linkage to other Project Outputs

This Chapter briefly shows how the work reported in this deliverable contributes to the general development workflow of the project.

This document deals with the integration and testing of the enablers created through WP2 activities hence, D2.9 primarily takes its feeding from a wide set of deliverables from WP1 (D1.x) and WP2 (D2.x), where the Use Cases, KPIs, the project architecture and enablers are collected while maintains alignment with the infrastructure description coming from WP3. The relationship between the work included in D2.9 and the rest of activities inside 5G-ROUTES is shown in Figure 1.

T2.5 aims at the validation and testing of a 5G Platform that coordinates the interaction between the set of enablers developed in WP2. T2.5 focuses on the cloud deployment capabilities of the enablers individually and their integration in a shared environment where they can communicate with other enablers at the earliest stages of the project. T3.3 “Integration and upgrade of 5G infrastructure of MNO networks in Finland, Estonia and Latvia with technological enablers” is closely linked to T2.5 since it will contribute to the definition of the 5G Infrastructure on top of which the 5G-ROUTES Platform will be working and therefore their interfaces and deployment requirements. Initial collaborations between the two have helped define the integration and deployment strategy and has driven the implementation description of the enablers. As soon as the underlying 5G Infrastructure is ready, T3.3 will ensure that the configured deployment strategy developed by T2.5 is compatible with the final infrastructure and will contribute seeking further compatibility if required.

Interactions with the preparation phase of other deliverables from WP3 and WP4 have contributed to define the most relevant information to include in D2.9. Their final content after submission will be used to elaborate the next deliverable of T2.5.

Figure 1 View of the relation between D2.9 and others 5G-ROUTES project deliverables

Table 2 D2.9 Contributions and Values of linkage

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Deliverable Chapter(s)	Contribution and Value of linkage
INPUTS from other deliverables utilised in this report		
D1.1 Use Cases and KPIs	Chapter 3, Chapter 5	Linkage: Specifications and requirements of the Use Cases. Contribution: How they will be addressed by enablers.
D1.5 Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM	Chapter 4	Linkage: Lists of performance indicators for the cross-border trials and test methodologies proposed for data gathering. Contribution: Enablers and Tenant Web Portal implementation contributions.

D1.7 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results	Chapter 3, Chapter 4, Chapter 5	Linkage: Information about the testing frameworks and the performance assessment process. Contribution: Definition of the testing guidelines
D2.1 AI Assisted Cross-Domain MEC and Integration Fabric for CAM Services	Chapter 6, Chapter7, Chapter 8	Linkage: Introduction to the 5G-ROUTES reference architecture and description of the enablers. Contribution: Implementation details of its enablers. Description of the 5G-ROUTES Platform and its relationship with the architecture of the project
D2.3 AI-based end-to-end slicing optimisation and innovative spectrum usage for CAM services	Chapter 7, Chapter 8	Linkage: Description of enablers. Contribution: Implementation details of its enablers. Relationship with the 5G-ROUTES Platform.
D2.5 AI-based positioning for V2X	Chapter 7, Chapter 8	Linkage: Description of enablers. Contribution: Implementation details of its enablers. Relationship with the 5G-ROUTES Platform.
D2.7 Tenant Web Portal implementation and deployment	Chapter 7, Chapter 8	Linkage: Description of Enablers. Contribution: Implementation details of its enablers. Relationship with the 5G-ROUTES Platform.

Table 3 Contributions of D2.9 from and to the rest of the deliverables.

OUTPUTS from this report utilised by other deliverables		
D3.3 CAM infrastructure development	Chapter 6, Chapter 8	Requirements and interfaces for the deployment of the enablers in the 5G infrastructure and how to connect with UCs.
D3.5 Lab trial findings	Chapter 6, Chapter 7, Chapter 8	Testing environment setup and overall 5G-ROUTES Platform definition to evaluate its performance.
D4.3 Performance evaluation and lessons learned	Chapter 7, Chapter 8	Entry point for devising the enablers validation in the trials. D4.3 will greatly contribute to the second deliverable of T2.5
D4.6 Performance evaluation	Chapter 7, Chapter 8	Entry point for devising the enablers validation in the trials. D4.6 will contribute to the second deliverable of T2.5

3 5G-ROUTES Integration Methodology

The Integration methodology proposed is twofold, it initially deals with the creation of a collection of procedures and guidelines meant to ensure that WP2 delivers a 5G-ROUTES Platform (see Figure 30) to a high standard compatible with a 5G testbed. Secondly, it is also home for the aggregated picture of the final set of enablers and their technical requirements as a way to configure an integration and deployment strategy for WP2, which will be then advanced by WP3 in order to adapt the 5G-ROUTES Platform deployment to the field trials infrastructure. Such Platform is built as the combination of innovative technological enablers developed within the project to comply with the needs of CAM UCs. It is part of the architecture of the 5G-ROUTES project [18] as was introduced in D2.1 and serves UCs as the gate to an underlying 5G infrastructure. It will be first tested in a controlled laboratory as part of WP2 prior to the actual production-grade tests in a field trial carried out by successive WPs.

3.1 Integration Objectives

T2.5 focuses on the cloud deployment capabilities of the enablers individually and their integration in a shared environment where they can communicate with other enablers at the earliest stages of the project. Cutting edge methodologies and tools in the context of software (SW) management and delivery are selected in this document as to align the integration objectives of WP2 with the development of enablers as soon as possible.

Regarding procedures, T2.5 efforts have been key to define a common workspace in which development teams have the required information to evolve their enablers following the same guidelines so that it will ease their integration with others and thus reduce the amount of work at late stages. At the same time, it will create a GitLab repository, working as the single source-of-truth reference point of the latest status and documentation from enablers which UCs will use as a living-document on how to use the enablers. Those procedures speak for the initial objectives of the document which are summarized below and will be disclosed throughout this document.

- Objective 1: Provide SW contribution guidelines based on a DevOps methodology with the GitLab CI/CD framework.
- Objective 2: Provide SW testing guidelines for enablers and the Platform that will show the required tools to meet the acceptance criteria established to approve the integration of new releases of the SW.
- Objective 3: Provide guidelines for the cloud deployment and integration of enablers which show the technologies planned to be used in pursuance of delivering a 5G-ROUTES Platform in a cloud-native environment compatible with the resources and infrastructure of the project.

D2.9 also acts as home of an aggregated picture of the collection of enablers that will be developed under the umbrella of T2.1, T2.2, T2.3 and T2.4. The information requested here offers insights on the implementation of enablers in favor of defining procedures targeting integration and deployment. This information has also contributed to combine the initial architecture of the project presented in D2.1 and the available information from testbeds and field trials coming from WP1 and WP3 to further define the 5G-ROUTES Platform and its deployment.

- Objective 4: Provide details of the final implementation of enablers considering the deployment and integration guidelines documented in this deliverable.
- Objective 5: Provide a description of the 5G-ROUTES Platform which will be offered as baseline for UCs to execute experiments in a stable release of enablers within the laboratory trials as well as for WP3 to further integrate enablers with the underlying 5G infrastructure of the field trials.

3.2 Integration Process Steps

Figure 2 depicts the 5 chronological steps that are planned as part of the integration process. The first milestone is completed at the time of submission of this deliverable and the second one is in progress (shown in green in Figure 2). That first milestone has resulted in the definition of a set of guidelines regarding software development and testing (Chapter 4 and 5), to encourage a unified workflow among partners that makes it possible to distribute the testing efforts throughout the development lifecycle of the enablers and the Platform. This approach will result in a highly comprehensive and consistent ecosystem even at early stages of the project. The 3rd milestone refers to the cloud deployment strategy to deliver a 5G-compatible Platform based on the information gained from the project’s architecture [18], the final set of technological enablers developed in WP2 and the 5G infrastructure configuration from WP3.

Figure 2 T2.5 internal milestones

In order to initiate milestone 3, it is first required to identify the final set of enablers arising from previous tasks along with some technical details of their expected implementation. Although the available details are limited due to their early stage of development, work has been done to shed some light on what the enablers will provide to enhance UCs as part of the 5G-ROUTES Platform (Chapter 7). This activity is key to create a reference blueprint of the Platform in terms of deployment environments and communications which is first introduced in Chapter 6 and then complemented in Chapter 8. As to obtain this information, a great deal of description coordination and detailed analysis of each individual enabler has been conducted in order to identify overlapping, dependencies and blocking issues. All these activities are being carried out as part of the weekly WP2 meetings and other issue-specific task-force teams that have been created to resolve multi-enabler and cross-WP issues.

Once all activities described here have been completed, UCs will be able to run rounds of experiments. After each round, Task 2.5 will analyze the performance results offered by WP4 (field trials results) to propose updates and improvements to enablers and oversee how the new releases follow the CICD pipelines and allow UCs to execute further rounds of experiments.

3.3 Integration Timeline

At the time of submission of the document, the CICD framework has not been tested since enablers are still in a design-stage with initial developments in their local premises. However, it should not be long until they have a sufficient level of maturity to be included in the proposed workflow. Table 4 shows a tentative timeline for the activities planned in T2.5.

Table 4 T2.5 activities timeline

Task Activities	Partners Involved	Deadline
Software and Testing Contribution Guidelines	ATOS	M9
CICD Framework Definition	ATOS	M9
Cloud Deployment Guidelines	ATOS	M16
Enablers technical description and timelines	ALL	M16
5G-ROUTES Platform description	ALL	M16
Enablers CICD framework implementation and validation	ALL	M19
5G-ROUTES Platform CICD framework implementation and validation	ATOS	M23
Integration tests development	ATOS	M23
WP4 results analysis	ALL	M28
D2.10 Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v2.0	ATOS	M36

According to Table 4, by the end of Q1 of 2022 all enablers shall have transferred the code of their enablers to the 5G-ROUTES GitLab working group (see Section 4.2) and have the CICD pipeline setup as explained in this document. As to achieve this, it is expected that a new WP2 series of meetings will be initiated for all developers to share their progress and align interfaces between each other at the beginning to 2022.

As soon as the previous activity is mature enough, a cross-WP task force will be created to update the deployment configuration of the 5G-ROUTES Platform to further align the testbed with the field trials.

By the end of WP2, the second report of T2.5 will be delivered containing all the knowledge acquired during the configuration of the CICD pipelines presented in D2.9 as well as the final set of tests and their results and progress for each individual enabler and for the Platform. Results from analysing D4.3 and D4.6 will also be included in the second report, specific actions over enablers will be extracted to enhance the UC experience.

4 5G-ROUTES Software Contribution Guidelines

Although T2.5 does not focus on the development of enablers, but rather just on their integration and testing, a set of guidelines and best practices have been agreed-upon to enhance the development practices among the consortium. Considering that, the target audience of this Chapter is mainly the development team from each partner that will be contributing towards the development of an enabler. It contains a set of background considerations that need to be understood from the very beginning of the development of any software since its objective is to drive it towards a uniform ecosystem.

An underlying CICD framework which shall help partners develop their enablers to a high level of quality and confidence is also described in this Chapter. The same CICD framework will also be used to trigger integration testing over a running 5G-ROUTES Platform that deploys the latest versions of each enabler and performs a suite of integration tests that should be able to provide enough confidence for UC to run their experiments in a full-fledge deployment.

Teams following the guidelines proposed here will have the tools to deliver production-grade software with a high level of confidence and reliability over the functionalities that they provide. It will then seamlessly integrate into any 5G infrastructure within the testbeds of the project thanks to the same mechanisms that made the software releasable and validated.

4.1 Introduction

During the evolution and maturity of the 5G ecosystem, the software (SW) industry has been under a major transformation in terms of methodologies and packetization techniques (containerization) which mainly translates to the adoption of a de-facto methodology of development and the automation of most of the day-to-day tasks. DevOps¹ is a way of developing a SW product based on the mutual benefits of combining developers and operation engineers into a shared framework. When correctly implemented, DevOps should aim to involucrate the whole team, offering flexible and yet reliable control checks with useful feedback that pays-off the extra overheads of such practice.

5G-ROUTES will exploit 5G technologies and features beyond research activities by means of delivering SW components offering a wide range of functionalities. A large number of partners of the consortium will be offering enablers and therefore it becomes crucial to put in place a shared methodology based on DevOps practices in order to ensure that their contributions are compatible with one another and serve a well-defined function in an integrated Platform.

Within the scope of the T2.5, a common and centralized software management solution will be provided to host and manage the code as well as to offer a window to the latest documentation of enablers for the UCs to review and learn how to benefit from it. The selection of the most appropriated solution, its configuration and maintenance will be undertaken as part of the initial activities of T2.5 and thus contained in this document.

4.1.1 Software Version Control

Version control (also known as source control) is the practice of tracking and managing changes to SW code. The purpose of such practice is to allow software developer teams to track changes to their code, while enhancing communication and collaboration between team members. Version control facilitates a continuous, simple way to develop software.

Source code acts as a single source of truth of a product's knowledge, history, and solutions [13]. It also serves as a safety net to protect the source code from irreparable harm, giving the development team the freedom to experiment without fear of causing damage or creating code conflicts in production environments. They are

¹ Combination of Software developers and System/Operation engineers

especially useful for DevOps teams since it helps them to reduce development time and increase successful deployments.

There are several widely used options for this purpose, the three most well-known options being: Gitⁱ, SVNⁱⁱ, and Mercurialⁱⁱⁱ. Looking at the Open-Source community within the 5G ecosystem (Opensource MANO (OSM^{iv}), Openstack^v, Opendaylight^{vi}, etc.) and to most of the projects in the 5G-PPP portfolio which 5G-ROUTES use as reference (5Genesis^{vii}, 5GMobix^{viii}, 5GSolutions^{ix}), it is clear that Git has been considered as the de-facto option and therefore it will be the one that will be used in the context of 5G-ROUTES.

4.1.2 Software Management Platform

Collaborative projects such as 5G-ROUTES greatly benefit from the use of a Git management platform, taking control over the shared repository in order to manage the collaboration and versioning for the integration of contributions before the service or application can be ready for production environment. These platforms also help simplify the administration of projects that target both product design and infrastructure configuration, which is the case of 5G-ROUTES.

There is an increasing market of software platforms for this purpose. A wide range of options are offered in the software market depending on the project's security policy, whether it is public or private, the size of the repository etc. Regardless of where the research is made, GitLab, GitHub and probably Bitbucket are the top three names that will appear (see Figure 3).

	Free users	Max repo size (GB)	Max file size (MB)	Max API calls per hour (per client)
GitHub	3	2	100	5000
BitBucket	5	1	Unlimited (up to repo size)	5000
GitLab	Unlimited	10	Unlimited (up to repo size)	36000

Figure 3 Comparison of Git management platforms [14]

The rapid adoption of new software techniques has resulted in the popularization of additional tools covering a specific portion of the development lifecycle, which is not directly related to the source code hosting. Under this group it may be found tools offering Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery (CICD) specific features such as Jenkins^x, CircleCi^{xi}, Bamboo^{xii}, Travis^{xiii}, Tox^{xiv} or some other tools covering the release's storage needs such as JFrog Artifactory^{xv}, DockerHub^{xvi}, PiPy^{xvii}, etc.

4.1.2.1 GitHub

GitHub [10] was founded in 2008 as a collaborating platform for developers in the form of Software as a Service (SaaS) and was quickly adopted by many developers and companies to host and manage their applications. As of January 2020, [3] GitHub boasts more than 40 million users, along with 100 million repositories.

Up until very recently, the use of the platform required a series of additional software tools to complete the development lifecycle of a product since it exclusively focused on code hosting. However, recent updates of their features include, particularly for the case of opensource and public repositories, the possibility of creating larger groups, larger storage etc. They have also introduced a novel CICD built-in framework but lacks on thoroughly explained documentation and since it is relatively new, most of its features continue to be updated and optimized. Although GitHub is currently hosting a large number of projects from the 5G-PPP portfolio, it is not considered to be a strong enough argument to overcome their restricted free storage policy and limited quantity of CICD minutes [10].

4.1.2.2 *GitLab*

GitLab [11] was founded in 2011. Starting as an opensource project to help teams collaborate on software development, GitLab is now a complete DevOps platform delivered as a single application. This means that it comes with a built-in CI/CD framework which enables teams to run automated tests quickly and for free.

One key aspect of this tool is that it works in SaaS mode under its own servers, GitLab.com, or self-hosted as a Community Edition software. Even if choosing to rely on GitLab.com, their free plan offers unlimited repositories and contributors in both private and public settings with a storage out at 10GB per repository [3]. Since it is a community-driven platform, there is an extensive step-by-step documentation on every feature that is released, and the community is very active and provides feedback at a high rate.

4.1.2.3 *Bitbucket*

Bitbucket [15] is the code management solution from the company Atlassian created in 2008. Its main clients are enterprises and businesses that are developing private, proprietary code [16]. Although offered as an independent product, Bitbucket offers a very limited set of functionalities other than the basic hosting mechanism for Git because the Atlassian objective is that other solutions should be used as well. For a software company to fully rely on Atlassian's products, Bitbucket should be integrated with [15] Jira, Confluence, Trello and Bamboo.

Regarding its pricing options, just for the case of Bitbucket with no integration with other products from the company, the terms and limits [10] show that it offers unlimited private and public repositories but for teams of less than 5 developers and in addition to this, the file storage is limited to 1GB.

4.2 5G-ROUTES Git Platform

As part of the 5G-ROUTES integration efforts, it is proposed to limit the number of third-party dependencies in alignment with the elaboration of several methodologies around the idea of a single source-of-truth reference point where it would be possible to extract the information of the entire lifecycle of each development in the project.

It has also been taken into account that 5G-ROUTES is a 22-partner consortium [20] in which most of them have interest in developing innovative solutions in many different areas. This translates in the need of having the flexibility to host a potentially large number of repositories and to allow partners to involve as many developers and contributors as they require.

Considering what was presented in Section 4.1.2, Bitbucket is discarded mainly due to its dependencies with additional software components from the company that provides it (Atlassian), leaving GitHub and GitLab as potential candidates that need some further comparison to identify the most convenient one for the project. Figure 4 shows the main free functionalities which are made available in each option. The difference used to be even larger before, but at this point in time GitLab still exceeds GitHub in the most important requirements that have been identified.

Free functionality	GitLab	GitHub
Private repositories	Yes	Yes
Number of collaborators	Unlimited	3
Wiki	Yes	No (public or paid only)
Pages	Yes	No (public or paid only)
Capacity	10GB	1GB
Indicates who is paying	No	Yes
Free CI	2,000 min.	Maybe a free tier for Actions on Azure
Entire DevOps lifecycle	Yes	No
Location of the repo	Anywhere	Not in groups/orgs
API concurrent rate limit	36000	5000

Figure 4 GitLab vs GitHub free functionalities [13]

5G-ROUTES will therefore make use of GitLab to host the complete collection of enablers and other developments which may arise from the project. One of the immediate advantages, as compared to other alternatives, is to have everything integrated under the same tool: GitLab source code management, Role-based access control, issues, documentation, a DevOps approach, and a full-fledge CI/CD framework. GitLab even provides a registry for each project which can be used to store containers, python wheels and other artefacts.

The platform has already been created in GitLab.com in the form of a Group named 5G-PPP-5G-ROUTES^{xviii} (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 5G-ROUTES GitLab Group named “5G-PPP-5G-ROUTES”

The 5G-PPP-5G-ROUTES platform will comprise a variety of groups and projects containing code from the technological enablers developed to improve the CAM services offered by UCs in the 5G-ROUTES infrastructure. It will additionally include integration-test-related repositories.

4.2.1 Reporting and Documentation

Regarding documentation hosting and versioning, GitLab offers a project-level Wiki which has its own internal history of changes. This is a great advantage since documentation updates do not necessarily require a new release, as it can be updated during the development timeline. The Wiki is a great feature for hosting user guides, trouble shootings, contribution guidelines and even changelogs and future work for a project. It is therefore

selected to serve as a living document of the latest version of an enabler where UCs that plan to use its features may find a clear guide on how to do so.

Very often, software product’s development is based on the concept of issues or tickets. Issues are essentially notes containing a certain work that needs to be carried out usually containing a small effort. This approach may not be so clear when starting a project from scratch, but it quickly becomes crucial as the codebase of the project expands and then when prioritization and versioning comes into the picture.

Figure 6 Workflow of Software Issues

At this moment in time, the status of most of the enablers correspond to the first two steps shown in Figure 6, which means that no actual development has started. However, the basic setup for the GitLab Group has been provided, and the common methodology has been agreed upon. Therefore, teams have been able to start planning the development activities in a more practical way by means of creating issues.

4.2.2 Artefact Registry

An artefact is a by-product created during the development of a software component. It can take many forms and degrees of openness, from a black-box approach all the way to a white-box component; binary, tar, docker image, Virtual Machine (VM) snapshot, configuration files, etc.

A registry is a service that maintains a list of artefacts. In the case of GitLab, it acts as a private or public registry for a variety of common package managers that can be published and consumed manually or by a Runner (see Section 4.2.6) executor.

The role of the GitLab artefact registry in the project will be centralized in a single repository to ease the execution of the planned CI/CD pipelines. It will be further explained later in this Chapter. It is worth mentioning that GitLab offers a dedicated artefact and cache registry for CI/CD pipelines which is not directly connected to the previous one. This new feature offers a way of sharing and exporting information from the internal execution of a job within a pipeline or to a downstream pipeline.

4.2.3 DevOps

DevOps [11] is an operational framework that is gaining followers, proving itself as a way to leverage the latest innovations from the software industry to the development lifecycle in a simplified way. Its base concept is to align software developments and its operation with Git in order to achieve three objectives:

1. Git as single source of truth of the system.
2. Git as the only place where the system is operated (create, change, and destroy all environments).
3. All changes are observable and verifiable. There is a CI/CD framework which allows to visualize the effects of each new code inserted in the codebase.

5G heavily relies on virtualization of infrastructures and automation which fall under the operation side of the software industry; thus, DevOps seems like a tailored-made methodology that will help 5G-ROUTES achieve its objectives.

Git offers many functionalities regarding change traceability and version management, known as Version Control System (VCS), but it does not enforce a specific sequence or strategy. It is rather assumed that the developer or group of developers will agree upon a common practice to accomplish work in a consistent and productive manner.

It is therefore expected that there will not exist a unified workflow across industries, but instead several successful workflows lead by different companies or organizations which may be taken as reference. The four base workflows are Centralised, Feature Branching, Gitflow and Forking [4]. It is not the intent of this document to explain each one in detail.

In 5G-ROUTES, Gitflow will be used as reference workflow in order to keep consistency and to provide a unified and fruitful ecosystem for development, testing and deployment. It establishes that each new repository starts with a master and a develop branch. The former will always hold official releases with a corresponding version tag and the latter serves as integration branch for all the new features that are to be added to the next release. DevOps stresses that contributions must follow a strict Merge Request and approval procedure since they will trigger the CICD framework which will eventually result in an update of the software artefact to be used in production environments. Applied to 5G-ROUTES, this means that each one of the features developed in an enabler must come from an additional branch which is merged into develop via Merge Request (MR).

According to the previous statements, the develop branch must never be updated via direct commit but via MR instead. Similarly, the master branch cannot be updated directly either. It is true, however, that the master branch may be updated in two different scenarios:

- A. An official release is planned: Then, a release branch should be created based on the latest commit on develop which should be part of the release and proceed as follow:
 1. Fully tests the release branch in integration or almost production environment.
 2. Update the changelog for the new release as well as the release number.
 3. MR to master.
 4. MR to develop.
- B. Given the scenario of a new bug which needs addressing in production environment either because it had not been replicated before or because it was introduced by a new release (right after the above scenario "A" in this list), then a hotfix branch should be created based on master and proceed as follow:
 1. Find the test which should have caught the given bug or add a new tests case replicating the said bug to ensure that it is fixed.
 2. Fix the bug.
 3. Update the changelog for the new release as well as the release number.
 4. MR to master.
 5. MR to develop.

Figure 7 Gitflow reference graph

Figure 7 shows an example of a git history in which all the previous scenarios have occurred. It is worth mentioning how develop and master are only ever directly connected when the repository is created.

4.2.4 Branch naming

Assuming that the proposed workflow from this document is undertaken, the main two branches are named just like described before, master and develop. Then, for the remaining branches, it is proposed to rely on Gitlab to create branches and MRs directly from the UI of each issue. That way it will be possible to have a fully detailed traceability of the changes, where they come from and who added it.

4.2.5 Merge Requests

Having a clean and easy to look at Git branch history can sometimes be crucial in order to find when something was added or broken. For this reason, a squash-based approach for merge commits is proposed and will be set as the default strategy in all repositories (see Figure 8).

Squashing allows the developer to combine every micro-commit from a branch into a single one, just before it is merged. GitLab greatly simplifies this process by automatically performing the compression of commits moments before it is merged to the target branch, thus keeping the entire history of micro-commits available up to the very end of its lifecycle. It also provides a way to summarize the most important progress into the squashed message of the commit and subsequently will lead to a straightforward master and develop branches with very clear commit messages.

Figure 8 Squash-based merge request commits

Regarding the lifecycle of branches, there is not a fixed amount of time when a branch must be deleted after it has been merged, but it is always recommended to keep as few branches alive as possible. Removing after merge is advised from local and remote repositories.

GitLab again offers most of these features built-in and ready to use by every developer. Figure 9 shows the Merge Request UI with the proposed options selected.

Figure 9 GitLab submit Merge Request UI

In the context of what should and should not be included to a Merge Request (MR), it is strongly recommended to use a specific-purpose IDE such as Sourcetree^{xi} or PyCharm^{xx} in order to add to the developer's Git routine the task of double-checking what files and the content of each one that was modified and that is staged to commit. This is especially important when realizing that every programming language and IDE produces a series of compiled or user-dependent files which could end up adding unnecessary weight to artefacts.

Although an initial ".gitignore²" file will be provided to every repository in order to ensure that the most common unwanted files are not added to the repository, it is recommended to consult the official GitHub page^{xxi} for some common templates based on the technology used.

The size of a MR is by no means fixed either and it can range from a single file to a whole structure refactoring. However, it is to bear in mind that a Merge Request is essentially work for other people to review and accept. Due to this, it will always be easier to review and provide meaningful comments on a small MR, a single

² File containing intentionally untracked files for Git to ignore.

functionality. Since a feature may be composed of several functionalities, it is proposed that one of the two options shown below are used depending on the preferences of the individual developer:

1. One feature branch may be used as target for smaller MRs during the development of a large feature. Then, once the entire feature is stable and tested in the said feature branch, the MR to develop may include a phrase like 'This Branch has been individually approved by previous MRs' and, in fact, such MRs are easily traceable looking at the branch history commits.
2. A different approach would be to use a single feature branch which is integrated to develop several times. Since a MR will only show difference between branches, consecutive MRs with the same branch to develop will only show advances from the previous merged commit of the feature branch.

In general terms a good MR is composed by; (1) Documentation, (2) Functionality, (3) Tests. Each of these changes should be checked by reviewers by going to the “changes” tab from the Merge Request UI of GitLab (see Figure 10).

Figure 10 GitLab Merge Request UI

Merge Requests are also an ideal place for hosting discussions, which are available as a secondary option when leaving a comment in the main MR page. Testing feedback is also collected in this view thanks to the underlying triggering of CI pipelines that will launch a new one for every new commit pushed to the branch that is under a MR revision.

4.2.6 CICD Framework

Continuous Integration (CI): is the practice of correctly combining the code as it is being developed by a team into a shared repository by building/testing each change automatically [11]. As early as possible and usually several times a day. Its main purpose is to detect errors as quickly as possible and to reduce integration debugging time by addressing smaller problems found at early stages.

This description can be translated into three very simple bullet points that should make it easy to understand the benefits from the CI methodology [11]:

1. Fail fast. Code conflicts and integration problems are discovered soon and if not, the CI pipeline should be modified. It is better to fix small problems often than to fix large problems seldom.
2. Always releasable. Even after a really unfruitful development period there should be at least something that is releasable.
3. Simple. All team members will be using this scheme every day, so the rules and routines must be clear and simple.

Continuous Delivery (CD): It goes one step further to enable a way to generate a verified version of the code and update the production environment with the latest features. According to [6], a CD pipeline takes the artefacts built by the CI pipeline and makes them available with a known tag and version to be later deployed. This pipeline prepares the software release and significantly reduces the manual tasks to just a few clicks. The literature often refers to Continuous Deployment as an interchangeable term but in reality, this last technique shall only be used when the human intervention is fully removed from the deployment lifecycle. Due to the characteristics of the 5G-ROUTES project, CD will be used to refer to the Continuous Delivery process.

Although there will be an automatic deployment of the enablers and of the 5G-ROUTES Platform carried out during CICD jobs, the deployment over the final infrastructures that UCs will use is not envisioned as part of T2.5.

GitLab CICD Framework: The framework results from the combination of two applications [11]; (1) GitLab Server, installed in any of its modes, takes the responsibility of hosting the source code and triggering CICD events based on the configuration provided by the project via a “.gitlab-ci.yaml” file. (2) GitLab Runner, i.e. the local server in the infrastructure that will be installed in the target environment, is the one that provides executors to run the pipelines when informed to do so by (1). This configuration is shown in Figure 11.

The built-in CICD framework from GitLab will help obtain production-grade software by means of a CI pipeline for the self-verification of the enablers and a CD pipeline for their packetization, tagging and storage.

The approach of GitLab greatly simplifies the connection to testbeds and, at the same time, provides a layer of security to the transaction based on temporal tokens that are only known by the two ends.

Figure 11 Gitlab CICD communication call flow

4.3 5G-ROUTES CICD

The adoption of a CICD framework is a procedure that accelerates the speed of developing hence, reducing the cost of service of the 5G-ROUTES enablers and its integration as a single Platform [1]. This feature correlates nicely with the iterative testing cycles proposed to conduct fields trials within the project since it will greatly simplify the process of improving and fixing the code of the enablers and achieve a rapid deployment of new versions.

Figure 12 5G-ROUTES CICD implementation

In the context of testing and integration, this task is twofold, it has first to implement a testing procedure over the development of the different enablers as they are built in isolation (see “enabler testing environment” in Figure 12), and secondly to ensure that they are able to interact with each other (see “5G-ROUTES Platform testing environment” in Figure 12). This correlates with the following chapters 5, 7 and 8 in the document where it is available the description of the integration acceptance criteria and what is being integrated for each case.

The expected sequence in Figure 12 considers that, at first, enablers are being developed as an isolated component in a dedicated repository with its corresponding CICD pipeline. At this moment of development, the enabler may be seen as 5G agnostic for it will not be deployed as part of a Network Service (NS) nor will have access to an underlying 5G infrastructure, functionalities are to be proved by means of using emulators and mocks. After the CI jobs finish correctly (yellow dots), a new candidate for release (testing version) will be published to the internal artefact registry of the project (hosted as a repository in GitLab) via CD jobs (red dots). Such event will trigger a downstream CICD pipeline in the integration repository. This last stage of automatized validation of enablers will make use of the 5G infrastructure of the testbed to deploy the complete 5G-ROUTES Platform in the form of an application compatible with the Network Function Virtualization (NFV^{xxiii}) ecosystem. Further information about this strategy is explained in Chapter 6 and Chapter 8.

In practice, Figure 13 depicts a Git diagram of the different scenarios that may result in an update of the enabler considering the methodologies presented in Section 4.2. The first output from Figure 13 should be that MRs to develop and master branches are the key triggering factors to the execution of the pipelines. However, and even though this scheme should be sufficient for most of the scenarios that may occur, GitLab offers a user-friendly interface which will allow developers to force a given pipeline to any branch as to provide more flexibility to the teams when they require so.

Figure 13 Enablers GitFlow with CICD trigger events

5 5G-ROUTES Testing Guidelines

In addition to analysing each enabler seeking synergies and synchronizing their interfaces, T2.5 will continue with the efforts that the 5G ecosystem is putting into aligning with the software industry in terms of advanced agility and state-of-the-art quality assurance tasks that are now available.

Testing methodologies have already been examined by previous tasks within 5G-ROUTES: T1.4 (D1.5 Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0) and T1.5 (D1.7 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0). They both introduce many important high-level concepts and frameworks regarding tests and validation of UCs, but there are still some requirements from the SW development perspective that needs to be addressed at the enabler level.

In particular, the agreed content of T1.4 includes that “The test process will fit neatly into the project’s iterative agile development process and allow for implementation of a Test-Driven Development methodology incorporating unit tests and acceptance tests.” Back to WP2, the T2.5 explains that [20] “The objective of this task is to perform the integration, configuration, and evaluation of the technological Enablers, to ensure they are compliant with the requirements and specifications specified in D1.1. Perform dry-run interworking tests to verify proper operation, functionality, and interoperability prior to live deployment in large-scale field trials. In this task, an evaluation of the performance capabilities of all technological enablers and the Tenant Web Portal will be conducted after every testing cycle, based on the outcomes of D4.3 to perform potential incremental improvements in their functionalities. In particular, to ensure the correctness of the ML algorithms at the positioning, MEC, network slicing and spectrum allocation subsystems in an integrated way, testing their reaction to changes in traffic and mobility patterns and simulating extreme events”.

Taking the above into consideration, WP2 plans to contribute with a suite of unit and functional tests as part of the codebase of each of the enablers that the consortium will produce. At this point it should become clearer how the CICD methodology nicely ensures that enablers are delivered to a high standard and provide their teams with the tools to automate the required tests. T2.5 introduces the idea of having an additional repository to host integration tests that will target the complete 5G-ROUTES Platform within a testbed. The objective here will be to ensure that enablers are compatible with the infrastructure where they will be deployed and that their interfaces are correctly configured to interact with other enablers.

5.1 Introduction

Modern development methodologies such as the ones presented in this document bring additional complexity to software management and quality assurance tasks. So much that indeed that testing has become part of the development process itself rather than being delegated to a separate process. In the context of 5G-ROUTES, two different CICD pipelines will be used, having each one of them a different scope and testing mechanisms.

Tests are also a way to ease the on-boarding process of a new developer to the team as well as to provide fine documentation on specific functionalities of the enabler. “Because the tests are written in the domain language, they act as a living documentation of our model. A new team member can read these tests to quickly understand how the system works and how the core concepts interrelate” [6].

5.1.1 Test Driven Development

Test Driven Development (TDD) is a common practice in software development, it makes the programmer focus on the requirements before writing the code [8]. This way, the developer codes a certain feature against a test which, when finished coding the feature, will prove that the functionality is achieved. TDD helps to build code that is correct and yields a reliable progress of the code as well as maintenance tasks such as refactoring without fear of regression [6].

Writing good tests that are not too slow, give a decent coverage and feedback and have very little dependency is not trivial and does not have a one-fits-all solution. It is also important to find the trade-off between the degree

of encapsulation and abstraction that makes a block of code more testable and the test-induced design hurdles [5].

TDD is sometimes referred to as the “Red, Green, Refactor” development cycle for the steps it involves. Figure 14 explains these steps and introduces the role of tests as the functional guard that ensures that a certain feature is achieved.

Figure 14 Test-Driven development

Even though the actual development of the enablers is in a very early stage and in fact TDD might not be applicable to the entire code base of an enabler, it is proposed that the development of enablers make use of this methodology to ensure that at least the most critical aspects and important functionalities are covered by tests. Thus, they will be able to guarantee that the iterative releases of the project are well tested and are reliable.

Tests are beneficial but it is important not to focus on a single type of test but instead distribute the efforts in a way that gives a good coverage of corner cases and is not prone to fail under small refactoring actions of the code. According to the Grant Agreement of 5G-ROUTES [20], tests should be categorized in three groups:

- Unit Tests are those that check small portions of code in an isolated way. Their scope must not be very broad, and no end-to-end business logic is expected at this point. A good design of the SW should enable unit tests with almost no mocks because it does not have external dependencies, their scope is to assert that, given some static input, the expected output is received. "Every line of code that we put in a test is like a blob of glue, holding the system in a particular shape. The more low-level tests we have, the harder it will be to change things." [2]
- Functional tests are those that check bigger pieces of code, potentially an entire functionality. Each functionality should be tested independently and mocking any external dependency to ensure that everything else other than the functionality under test, is using static, well-known data. Just like unit tests, it should assert that the expected output is achieved.
- Integration tests, also known as end-to-end tests, are those that check APIs against an actual system with some level of operation enabled. They make use of limited operational versions of the code's dependencies (dry-run versions) which ensure that the interaction between components is correct but will not carry-out the underlying operation.

Apart from the previous types of tests, there exist others that may be required depending on the project. Namely Smoke Tests, System tests, Regression tests and Performance & Load tests. In the context of 5G-ROUTES, code

quality tests will also be used automatically thanks to the CICD pipeline of the enabler. This type of tests performs static validation of syntax and rules depending on the language used.

5.2 Enablers and Tenant Web Portal Testing

In view of Chapter 4, it is proposed that each enabler, including the Tenant Web Portal (TWP), incorporate into its codebase a set of tests that demonstrate the core functionalities that they are offering to the project. These tests will be automatically executed on each proposed update of the enabler through a CICD pipeline. The timeline of the releases of enablers is shown in Figure 21 which is built based on the aggregation of the information from Chapter 7.

The acceptance criteria to consider that the enabler is suitable to be integrated in the 5G-ROUTES Platform is that said pipeline must provide information about:

1. The level of coverage in terms of lines of code tested
2. Static code quality score based on a linter³ for the corresponding technology used
3. A collection of tests that verify that the core functionalities offered to UCs are met.
4. A virtualization mechanism compatible with the overall deployment guidelines presented in this document.

5.2.1 Unit Test

According to the TDD methodology, unit tests in 5G-ROUTES are to be provided by the development team of each enabler at the same pace as the actual code is developed. Here, a collection of fast and probably abstract tests of small portions of code will help achieve a good base coverage so that typos, syntax errors and any other broken piece of code is detected as early as possible.

As to achieve this, unit tests should only focus on small methods that do not have dependencies on external services or on pieces of code that perform low level changes such as IO changes, database queries etc.

5.2.2 Functional Tests

Similarly to unit test case, these functional tests should also be provided along with the code of the enablers although, in this case, T2.5 will help guiding teams to improve them after each testing cycle to ensure the correctness of the ML algorithms and main services offered to the UCs by the different enablers.

The objective of functional tests is to probe an entire functionality under an isolated test environment with no external dependencies. They may be used for more time-consuming tests, checking a large range of inputs and corner cases. For the sake of maintainability, this type of tests should have the ability to inject dependencies into the normal workflow of the system and to fall back to mocks of external services, so it is possible to test larger portions of code without the need of a production-like environment.

In the context of 5G-ROUTES, they will help partners developing enablers to prove that they comply with the requirements and expected functionalities introduced in D1.1. Additional validation will come from the UC experiments, their measures and experience with each enabler.

5.3 5G-ROUTES Platform Testing

Besides the tests shown in Section 5.2, T2.5 aims to offer an additional layer of confidence for successive WPs and UCs to consider that the enablers perform correctly. In this case, an additional repository in GitLab has been created to host the configuration scripts and NFV descriptors that will be used to deploy the collection of enablers in the correct cloud environment ensuring network connectivity among them.

³ A tool that analyzes source code to flag programming errors, bugs, stylistic errors, and suspicious constructs.

Said repository will also provide a way to automate the conformance of the acceptance criteria thanks to a suite of integration tests that perform validations of the inner enablers in an aggregated way.

1. The Platform is delivered in a 5G-compatible artefact that can be deployed through the 5G orchestrator available in the testbed. According to Section 6.3, the CTTC testbed is the most suitable environment to test E2E the functionalities of the 5G-ROUTES Platform and therefore ETSI OSM will be used in WP2 integration while WP3 will assist enablers to adapt to the Ericsson Orchestrator as is the one that will be deployed in field trials [18].
2. Enablers shall prove that they interact with each other in a multi-cloud-based deployment
3. Enablers offer a configuration that allow to perform close-to-production operations in a dry-run test.

As integration tests rely on an actual infrastructure to be performed, they are not expected to be developed along with the previous types of test but rather included in the shared efforts of T2.5 and T3.3. Dev teams however are expected to provide the necessary information and resources to conduct a successful deployment and test of the enabler. They will also need to add a way for the enabler to be configured in a dry-run mode, meaning that the interfaces shall be accessible but the underlying functionalities do not need to be executed at this point.

5.3.1 Integration Tests

These tests will be developed last since they require a certain level of maturity from the enablers. At this point in time, it is been actively researched the common test tools used by the industry and standardization [19] organizations so that 5G-ROUTES has the means for leveraging relevant results from past projects and working groups. Regarding the actual language to perform the test in, the first two candidates are RobotTest [22] and Pytest-bdd [23]. It is not the aim of this document to explain any of the two libraries in detail, but it is enough with understanding how they both provide a way for the non-technical teams to read and understand tests that verify end-to-end functionalities.

By correctly utilizing RobotTest and pytest-bdd, 5G-ROUTES will be able to provide a test suite that builds a bridge between the business and the developer members of the project. This additional layer of testing provides information about:

1. Breaking changes in the API of a new release of an enabler since it will run a set of scenarios that requires the inner components of the 5G-ROUTES Platform to interact between each other.
2. End to end checks on functionalities involved in the scenarios.
3. Dependency checks to raise inconsistencies between an enabler's expected input/output and the actual requirements from the remaining enablers.

The underlying checkpoints that will be verified will target the interaction and call flows between enablers as well as configuration correctness once deployed. At the time of submission of D2.9 the exact interfaces and sequence of messages between each enabler are not fully clear yet, therefore, the current work carried out has been dedicated to drive the definition of the enablers within the WP2, synergies, responsibilities, and communication mechanisms while the actual test suite will be provided in the upcoming deliverable of T2.5.

6 5G-ROUTES Platform Cloud Deployment Guidelines

In addition to guidelines, procedures, alignment of enablers and support on testing, T2.5 has contributed to set the grounds for the deployment strategy of enablers. The objective is to integrate enablers into a coordinated 5G-ROUTES Platform which interconnects enablers according to their needs (further explained in Chapter 7). This definition of deployment will serve upcoming WPs to further define the enabler-to-Infrastructure interfaces at the testbed and field trial level.

Following the latest trends in the SW development industry, 5G-ROUTES will make use of virtualized infrastructures to deploy enablers in the form of NFV, most probably CNFs. In the 5G-ROUTES project, virtualization will be provided by the NFVI layer through a 5G Orchestrator, either ETSI OSM at the testbed trials or the Ericsson Orchestrator in the field trials [18]. This strategy ensures that the enablers shall be deployed both at the testbed and field trial infrastructure with no ad-hoc access and privileges required. By using a container-based NFV approach [28], it provides a flexible environment where the 5G-ROUTES technological enablers can be deployed at the optimal location during UC testing while being compatible with a local deployment for isolated testing with not much difference.

6.1 Introduction

Virtualization is an approach to network architectures that focuses in reducing the degree of dependency that traditional network elements have with the physical equipment. Decoupling the functionality from the underlying hardware permits a more flexible and standardized evolution of network elements and consequently reducing the overall costs and opening potential paths for a more autonomous network management and players.

6.1.1 Network Function Virtualization

NFV (Network Function Virtualization) is a specification produced by the ETSI ISG NFV group [28] which is key to fully leverage the potential of 5G. It introduces a framework that exploits the IT technologies for virtualizing network elements as modular software components called Network Functions (NF) that can be executed over COTS servers. The final goal of this paradigm is to migrate from the traditional infrastructures where processes reside in specific network nodes to architectures where the functionalities are provided by microservices running over general-purpose equipment in a distributed manner.

The use of virtual machine and containers in NFV reduces the HW dependencies and allows creating flexible networks that react and adapt on running time to changes in platform operations by means of programming and AI-based decisions. The NFV framework distinguish between three different kinds of implementations for the functional components inside the virtualized platform which builds-up a Network Service (NS):

- **Virtual Network Functions (VNF)**, applications deployed using virtual machines over a hypervisor belonging to the cloud infrastructure.
- **Physical Network Functions (PNF)**, software delivered embedded in a custom hardware element.
- **Container Network Functions (CNF)** also referred as **Cloud-native Network Functions**, software distributed as a container running inside a virtualized platform.

NFs are managed and monitored by the MANO NFV element (5G orchestrator), which provides the tools for handling the NFs lifecycle.

In the context of T2.5, enablers are planned to be offered as CNFs and therefore it is the most relevant type of NFV to be covered in this document. Anyway, more detailed information about NFV is to be found in D3.3 "Report on CAM infrastructure development in vehicles, railways and maritime v1.0" along with the set of CAM Services NSs that will be created by the UCs.

CNF maintains the principle of decoupling the software functionality from the HW platform by packaging the applications and their dependencies into isolated lightweight boxes. Built using a microservices architecture,

they are dynamic, flexible, and easily scaled, meaning that each CNF is comprised of small independent processes or elements which all communicate with each other and enable a modular approach to system building. These properties make CNF a favored solution in the transition to 5G.

6.1.2 Containers

According to K8s [31], containers are similar to VMs (see Figure 15), but they have a lower degree of isolation properties since they share the Operating System (OS) among every container running in the same host. But they do have their own filesystem, share of CPU, memory, process space etc. Containers are therefore decoupled from the underlying infrastructure, but they are lightweight and portable across clouds and OS distributions.

Figure 15 Deployment History of Setups [31]

Containers have become very popular in all markets and verticals. Some of the extra benefits that it is able to provide [31] include:

- Agile application creation and deployment: Increased ease and efficiency of container image creation compared to VM image use.
- Continuous development, integration, and deployment: Provides for reliable and frequent container image build and deployment with quick and efficient rollbacks (due to image immutability).
- Environmental consistency across development, testing, and production: Runs the same on a laptop as it does in the cloud.
- Cloud and OS distribution portability: Runs on Ubuntu, RHEL, CoreOS, on-premises, on major public clouds, and anywhere else.
- Application-centric management: Raises the level of abstraction from running an OS on virtual hardware to running an application on an OS using logical resources.
- Loosely coupled, distributed, elastic, liberated micro-services: Applications are broken into smaller, independent pieces and can be deployed and managed dynamically – not a monolithic stack running on one big single-purpose machine.
- Resource isolation: Predictable application performance.
- Resource utilization: High efficiency and density.

In the context of 5G-ROUTES, NFV micro-services are [28] atomic service modules, delivered as an all-inclusive SW package, that covers a specific and coherent functional scope, is consumable over network interfaces, is managed independently from other micro-services, and runs as a computing process.

6.1.3 Kubernetes

Kubernetes (K8s) [31] is a portable, extensible, open-source platform for managing containerized workloads and services, that facilitates both declarative configuration and automation. It has a large, rapidly growing ecosystem in which services, support, and tools are widely available.

While docker [31] makes it easier to create, deploy and run applications with the use of containers. Kubernetes is used for automating deployment, scaling and management of the containers. It also solves one of the biggest problems with container-based deployment which is how all the containers should be coordinated and scheduled.

6.1.4 Cloud-Native Infrastructure Service

According to the description offered by ETSI, Cloud-Native (CN) is a software design principle with certain properties and a set of non-functional characteristics [28]. Therefore, a CN infrastructure service (CNIS) that supports such design principle shall offer a service that provides runtime environment (see Figure 15) for one or more container virtualization technologies. This service can run on top of a bare metal or hypervisor-based virtualization [28].

6.2 5G-ROUTES Platform Deployment

Figure 16 has been extracted from D2.1 to illustrate the latest version of the architecture of the project that is been developed to support 5G-ROUTES in field trials. An initial description of each component is available in the aforementioned deliverable and will be further documented in deliverables from WP3. Since WP2 only targets at the delivery of the enablers (green components in Figure 16), Figure 30 and Chapter 8 shall be used to visualize what WP2 will provide as the 5G-ROUTES Platform as well as its relevant interfaces. The 5G-ROUTES Platform is to be understood as the coordinated integration and deployment of all enablers offered by WP2. Here, it is shown as two separated clouds depending on where the enablers will be deployed. This will be further justified in Chapter 7 and 8.

Figure 16 5G-ROUTES Project Architecture [18]

As far as this deliverable is concerned, the most important findings of WP3, summarized in D2.1 and Figure 16, relate to the cloud infrastructures and the accessibility to them as to prepare the integration plan for the 5G-ROUTES Platform in the first stages of the project. This will ultimately ensure the capabilities of enablers to be deployed in the field trials and to communicate with each other. D2.1 indicates that field trials will support the deployment of cloud-native Network Services through the interfaces offered by the EO (see Figure 16) which was confirmed by Ericsson as the only way to leverage the virtualized infrastructures in field trials. Moreover, the 5G-ROUTES project is not initially aiming to provide a shared cloud in the infrastructure of hyperscalers such as Amazon Web Services or Google Cloud Platform [32] which further drives the integration plan developed in T2.5.

After aligning Figure 16 and the available list of enablers from Chapter 7, it is clear that the integration of enablers into the 5G-ROUTES Platform shall provide a way for some enablers to be deployed at the edge (as close as possible to the UCs) while others may remain at the core cloud infrastructure of the domain. The former will be referred to as the 5G-ROUTES Edge Cloud and the latter as the 5G-ROUTES Core Cloud. This type of multi-cloud deployment scenarios has already been analyzed by ETSI [25] [26] [27] and the proposed use cases are currently under research to fully define the 5G-ROUTES deployment strategy.

It is known at this stage from interactions with WP3 and WP4 partners, that enablers in WP2 should include in their planning a way to offer their solutions in a virtualized environment, docker containers over Kubernetes mainly. This approach will allow developers to have the freedom to initially work on their enablers in a local environment without much overhead related to the use of a specific infrastructure since both technologies (docker and Kubernetes) are easily installed locally.

5G-ROUTES has an additional complexity that the deployment must take into account. That is the fact that the UCs will be based on vehicles moving from one Mobile Network Operator (MNO) domain to another across a border. D2.1 explains how this is addressed in-depth providing information on how the 5G-ROUTES Platform is essentially duplicated at each domain and inter-connected through a cross-domain bridging configuration of the Integration Fabric MQTT Broker enabler. This greatly reduces the cloud infrastructure required by the project since there is no need for a cloud hosted in a third-party infrastructure outside the resources of the MNOs that take part of the project.

6.2.1 Deployment Strategy and Requirements

Considering the description of the existing testbeds (Section 6.3), T2.5 and T3.3 are collaborating to configure a deployment strategy that best suits the interests and objectives of the two tasks. This document presents a strategy that will offer an automated deployment of the 5G-ROUTES Platform in a testing environment while T3.3 will only need to slightly adjust it since it is more interested in a fully working deployment that leverages all of the 5G resources offered by an infrastructure either at the lab or field trials.

Figure 17 depicts a strategy based on NFV (refer to Section 6.1) that is fully compatible not only with the testbed [24] and field UC experiment trials, but it is also suitable to be used by the 5G-ROUTES Platform CICD in a testing environment. That way, WP2 intends to provide a baseline validation of the Platform as early as possible to successive WPs so that they can concentrate in its use and performance testing. Regarding the first stage of testing, it was previously mentioned that, by providing a containerized application, enablers will be able to fully leverage the tools offered by the configured GitLab CICD pipeline. Chapters 4 and 5 have already shown the technologies that will be used to provide an automated testing deployment of the Platform. The exact installation guides for the GitLab Runners and their registration at the GitLab server is well documented online.

Figure 17 5G-ROUTES deployment strategy in T2.5

6.2.1.1 5G Orchestrator

By using the same 5G orchestrator that will be provided to instantiate the Network Services of UCs (CAM Services), the project is avoiding conflicts with limited accessibility to the underlying infrastructures when dealing with a commercial environment (see Figure 17). It is already known that the initial infrastructure that WP2 will have available at the testbeds will slightly differ from the one available at field trials. In particular, ETSI Open-Source MANO (OSM) is going to be used at the lab environment testbed instead of the 5G Orchestrator from the Ericsson solution (EO) that will be used for the field trials (see Figure 16). Since the EO solution is under development at the time of submission of this deliverable, it is the intent of WP3 to ensure that the orchestrator interfaces are as similar as possible in the two cases. More details about this issue will be disclosed within upcoming WP3 deliverables.

OSM is a well-known ETSI-hosted project providing a Management and Orchestration (MANO) stack aligned with the ETSI NFV Information Models. As a community-led project, OSM delivers a production-quality MANO stack that meets requirements from operators for commercial NFV deployments [24]. The installation of OSM shall be carried out taking care of the detailed installation procedure offered by the OSM guides^{xxiii}. It is recommended that OSM is installed in a single-node k8s cluster which shall not be used as one of the connected clusters to deploy Cloud-native Network Functions (CNF, also referred to as KNF in OSM literature). However, such k8s installation is planned to be used to host the GitLab runners, see Figure 17, so that the execution of the CICD jobs can easily connect to OSM and therefore ease the integration validation tasks.

Current description of the available testbeds from Section 6.3 indicate that they will install ETSI OSM Release 9 (release 10 will be evaluated depending on the level of maturity). This insight offers some clear requirements for the artefacts that will compose the 5G-ROUTES Platform to be compatible with it in terms of the technologies that can be used and the versions and specifications that must be supported in the information model describing the NFV artefacts.

Figure 18 OSM alignment with ETSI specifications [30]

Figure 18 depicts the complete set of specifications that OSM is based on. As far as the integration task is concerned, the 5G-ROUTES Platform will be described in the form of a NFV artefact compatible with SOL006, SOL002, SOL004 [28] which are further described in Chapter 6.2.1.3. They will then be onboarded to OSM and later instantiated through its SOL005-compliant North Bound Interface API (see Figure 19). The exact API calls to be used will slightly differ depending on the final lab infrastructure and setup and thus included in the next report of this task.

Figure 19 OSM North Bound API

6.2.1.2 Cloud-Native infrastructure

As introduced in Section 6.1, NFV deployments based on containerized applications such as the technological enablers developed in 5G-ROUTES (refer to Chapter 7) require a CNIS, which in the case of OSM shall be offered through a Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) [29]. Chapter 6.3 details how each testbed will provide said layer, then, OSM will be connected to it in one of the permitted schemas [30].

Figure 17 shows a scenario that makes use of two additional clouds connected to OSM so that it is possible to distribute the internal VNFs of the 5G-ROUTES Platform NS. This will contribute to the optimized interaction between UC and enablers since Edge enablers will be deployed as close as possible to the UE of UCs and thus capable of providing a minimal latency when using the services offered by the enablers. For the case of OSM, this can be achieved in several ways and in fact, some of them are documented in its User Guides^{xxiv}

The SW and HW requirements of the 5G-ROUTES Platform is tightly linked to the final implementation of enablers and therefore, not yet possible to establish due to their stage of development. However, an initial set of tools and requirements of the infrastructure where enablers will be hosted has been identified and transferred to WP3 and testbed owners for them to start the provisioning and configuration activities.

- Helm^{xxv} 3 installed. Helm will help manage the Kubernetes applications through CNFs based on Helm Charts. These charts ease the definition, installation, and upgrade of even the most complex Kubernetes application.
- Persistent volume storage configured. Chapter 7 and 8 explain how UCs and enablers require of a way to persist metrics and logs of their performance and overall experiment execution. The Tenant Web Portal is planned to be used as the single gateway to a long-term storage database (see Figure 31) to comply with such requirement. This is part of the OSM installation procedure and therefore easily extractable to configure the remaining clusters.
- Service exposure configured with a load balancer or similar. Having enablers deployed in different clusters will require a way for them to correctly resolve and reach the services. This is part of the OSM installation procedure and therefore easily extractable to configure the remaining clusters.
- Exact HW requirements are not yet clear. Considering the available information from Chapter 7, a conservative requirement with sufficient resources will be provided by any of the testbeds of the project with no issues. Final numbers will be contained in the next report of this task.
- Secure exposure and access to the internet. This will be first required during the installation of the GitLab runners in order to connect the code repositories to the testbed. UC experimenters will also need a way to reach the instance of the Tenant Web Portal as to configure, start, and monitor an experiment.

6.2.1.3 5G-ROUTES Platform artefacts.

The 5G-ROUTES Platform artefacts will be composed of OSM-compatible descriptors and the docker images that go along with them. These descriptors might be individual for each enabler or integrated into a multi-enabler one depending on the final setup of the testbeds and possibilities offered by OSM. Figure 20 shows an example provided by OSM which makes use Helm to deploy a CNF (KNF in the context of OSM) which will be used as reference to produce the artefacts of the 5G-ROUTES Platform.

Either way, the deployment of the 5G-ROUTES Platform shall be aligned with the previous Section 6.2.1 and the overall architecture of the project (see Figure 16). It shall allow developer team of enablers to detail the enabler-specific SW and HW configuration as well as network connectivity.

```

nsd:
  nsd:
    - description: NS consisting of a single KNF openldap_knf
      designer: OSM
      df:
        - id: default-df
          vnf-profile:
            - id: openldap
              virtual-link-connectivity:
                - constituent-cpd-id:
                    - constituent-base-element-id: openldap
                      constituent-cpd-id: mgmt-ext
                virtual-link-profile-id: mgmtnet
              vnf-id: openldap_knf
            id: openldap_ns
            name: openldap_ns
            version: '1.0'
          virtual-link-desc:
            - id: mgmtnet
              mgmt-network: 'true'
          vnf-id:
            - openldap_knf

vnfd:
  description: KNF with single KDU using a helm-chart
  df:
    - id: default-df
      ext-cpd:
        - id: mgmt-ext
          k8s-cluster-net: mgmtnet
      id: openldap_knf
      k8s-cluster:
        nets:
          - id: mgmtnet
      kdu:
        - name: ldap
          helm-chart: stable/openldap
        mgmt-cp: mgmt-ext
        product-name: openldap_knf
        provider: Telefonica
        version: '1.0'

```

Figure 20 Simple NSD (left) with a single CNF (right)

6.2.2 Deployment Timeline

The chart shown in Figure 21 is built on top of the information gathered in Chapter 7 and, identifies the enablers that will be validated in the corresponding 5G-ROUTES laboratory testbed, and highlights the several releases of the developed component. This offers an initial expected release date of all enablers by M22 when it will be

resource that some of the enablers require but, in most cases, a full-fledge UC test may not be feasible due to the highly specialized setup of the testbed. Only CTTC testbed will be able to host a fully deployed 5G-ROUTES Platform with most of the functionalities available.

On top of the three main testbed that are covered in this Chapter, partners have expressed their intention to initiate the development of their enablers in their own premises at the earliest stage of development until the design and requirement stage is fully closed.

6.3.1 CTTC testbed

CTTC NFV Infrastructure is not a unified one, but instead a collection of smaller customised instances of different components (e.g., not a single OpenStack but many smaller ones, each one configured towards a specific end). This is purposefully done as to isolate research environments. Partners and Use Cases should clearly define such requirements as CTTC “Testbed Instances”, which CTTC will deploy accordingly.

6.3.1.1 Resources

NFVI is usually deployed on top of VMs leveraging Infrastructure as Code (IaC) tools, such as Ansible, OpenStack, LXC and Kubespray. As for the RAN, this resource is currently shared among NFVIs/Network Slice Instances (NSI), therefore its use needs to be coordinated among experimenters.

CTTC does not maintain a storage infrastructure, therefore statelessness of deployments is encouraged.

Regarding the availability of K8s clusters, it can be deployed within an Openstack instance, or standalone. Either way, CTTC will deploy leveraging Kubeadm via Kubespray, which constrains the version to be used.

Overall, capacity installed within the CTTC testbed is found below. It is worth mentioning that 5G-ROUTES is not the only tenant of the testbed and therefore resources need to be agreed and selected with a low requirements perspective.

- 4 x 32 Intel Xeon CPU 3.9GHz
 - 4 x 386GB RAM
- 2 x 48 Intel Xeon CPU 3.2GHz
 - 2 x 192GB RAM
- 10TB SSD Storage (Data Center)
- 8 x 4 Intel i7 CPU 4GHz (Intel NUC)
 - 8 X 16GB RAM (Intel NUC)
 - 8 x 256GB SSD Storage (Intel NUC)

Regarding the installation of OSM as underlying MANO for the project, as OSM may only represent a single, rather lightweight VNF/CNF, we may instantiate one per UC. It is a common practice in the testbed to avoid sharing resources between UCs as to prevent unforeseen incompatibilities.

6.3.1.2 Accessibility

Access to CTTC testbed must be coordinated and responsible persons should be registered by CTTC IT team. Relevant required information includes:

- Name of partner involved.
- Email.
- Public IP from which the partner will access CTTC VPN.

Once this information is received by CTTC, access to the partners with the specified Public IPs will be granted. From the testbed side we enforce routing rules, as to only allow access to agreed resources (e.g., networks, GPUs,

etc.) SSH access to resources is preferred⁴, but a GUI desktop environment may also be configured leveraging LXDE and xRDP.

6.3.2 TTU testbed

The 5G testbed offered by TTU which will be used in 5G-ROUTES has three setups:

- 5G NR Positioning Opensource Testbed for PRS measurements (mostly used for research activities, see Appendix 3 in D2.5)
- 5G Non-stand Alone (NSA) Test Network (see Section 5.1 in D2.5)
- 5G Stand Alone (5G-SA) testbed (see Section 5.2 in D2.5)

6.3.2.1 Resources

The host provided in TTU testbed has limited resources which will probably limit the number of installed enablers and experiments running in parallel. TTU's procedure is actually to connect an experimenter's local host to the required 5G components from the testbed and therefore they should be the ones to bring any extra capacity required by their tests.

- **Ubuntu 18.04 LTS** Operating System,
- **64 GB** of RAM,
- **8 CPUs**,
- **300 GB** of free storage space.

6.3.2.2 Accessibility

Access to third parties (i.e., project partners other than TTU) has not been done at the moment, but it is possible to grant remote access through e.g. SSH or a GUI desktop environment may also be configured. This requires further investigation.

6.3.3 VTT testbed

The Tampere testbed is hosted by Business Tampere. The testbed is currently a pre-5G network and is planned to be upgraded to 5G. The network has a MEC server. However, application deployment at the MEC currently is not possible remotely, and requires physical access to the MEC, which has to be negotiated with the City of Tampere.

VTT has also access to the 5GTN test network in Otaniemi, Oulu and Sodankylä, and has also a MEC deployed in the 5GTN test network in Oulu. These facilities will also be used to test MEC functionalities. Other possibilities are to use SSH tunnelling to VTT's own servers in Tampere.

6.3.3.1 Resources

The testbed has limited resources for virtual machines. Information to be provided later to interested parties.

6.3.3.2 Accessibility

Access to third parties (i.e., project partners other than VTT) has not been granted at the moment and will be negotiated with the interested parties.

⁴ Sometimes, changing the MTU=1200 of the VPN-facing interface is required.

7 5G-ROUTES Enablers and Tenant Web Portal

The type of information provided in Chapter 7 is different from the previous content of the deliverable because it does not offer additional guidelines or methodologies. Instead, the objective of this Chapter is to offer a single point of reference for the technical information of all enablers related to their implementation as well as their development timeline to T2.5 and other interested WPs so that an aggregated integration timeline can be established.

In the context of T2.5, an enabler is a piece of software that facilitates an enhancement or new functionality to the 5G Infrastructure or to a UC CAM Service Application in the form of a NFV micro-service (see Chapter 6.1). enablers have an additional commitment to the project and T2.5, which is that they plan to be used all the way from the testbed stage to the large-scale field trials. Other research activities are envisioned as part of previous tasks in WP2 and might result in enablers if they are proved useful to UCs and the required resources available at the field trials. A coordinated integration and deployment of all enablers conform what has been defined as the 5G-ROUTES Platform (see Figure 16).

As to elaborate the different guidelines and procedures from D2.9, each enabler was requested to provide information that is relevant to comply with the validation of the acceptance criteria covered in Section 5.2.

1. Requirements related to hardware, software and communication needs
2. Interfaces to describe who uses the enabler and who the enabler relies on to obtain its relevant information.
3. Usability which translates into the type of artefact in which the enabler is embedded (docker image, AI/ML model, python package etc).

Additionally, it is relevant to understand if the enabler is planned to contribute to the end-to-end orchestration of UC CAM Services (the VNFs that the UCs will create) as part of the 5G-ROUTES Platform (see Chapter 8) or if it is planned to offer specific functionalities for the UCs to actively consume. This classification was already introduced in Chapter 6.2 as it is part of the overall 5G-ROUTES architecture presented in D2.1.

1. Core enablers: They enhance a horizontal functionality provided at the 5G Infrastructure level. They will be deployed as part of the 5G-ROUTES Platform Core Cloud.
2. Edge enablers: Those that are provided at the service level (CAM Services from Use Cases) to exploit an advanced functionality directly from the UC applications.

According to the GA, integration and testing shall be carried out all the way from the testbed to extended field trials. T2.5 will focus on the activities located at the testbeds for all those enablers shown in Table 5 during the first stage of the project, leaving to WP3 the integration in field trials. Table 5 is complemented in Chapter 8 with Table 17, where the enablers, and therefore the 5G-ROUTES Platform as a whole, are mapped against the different UCs of the project providing a clear view of where each enabler will be used and how the functionalities that the enablers offer respond to specific UC's needs.

Table 5 Summary of Technological Enablers

Enabler Name	Enabler Type	Lead Partners	Main Contribution	Reference in D2.9	Reference in WP2 deliverables
Integration Fabric	Core	IQU	Platform communications and UC metrics redirection to TWP Database	Section 7.1.1	D2.1
Network Slicing for CAM Services	Core	CTTC	Optimized network slicing for UCs	Section 7.2.1	D2.3

CAM Repository	Core	ATOS	Stores and distributes VNFs and their requirements (images) from the UC CAM Services to the infrastructure	Section 7.1.2	D2.1
Tenant Web Portal	Core	EBOS	UC experimenter's UI to start an experiment and data collector for the project	Section 7.4	D2.7
Slice Negotiator	Core	WINGS	Instantiation of UC's CAM Services in both domains	Section 7.2.2	D2.3
Resource allocation and positioning of V2X related NFs	Core	CERTH	Optimization of UC CAM Services positioning and resources	Section 7.1.4	D2.1
5G network-based positioning and 5G integrated hybrid positioning	Core + Edge	TTU	Enhanced positioning information	Section 7.3.2	D2.5
Assisted handover in cross borders	Edge	WINGS	UC VNF IP connectivity recovery	Section 7.1.3	D2.1
Low-latency cross-border synchronisation mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery	Edge	CERTH	UC VNF state migration	Section 7.1.5	D2.1
V2X routing using MEC	Edge	VTT	UC communications in MECs	Section 7.1.6	D2.1
5G localization for VRU protection	Edge	CERTH	Enhanced localization information	Section 7.3.1	D2.5

7.1 AI Assisted Cross-domain MEC and Integration Fabric for CAM Services

This Chapter covers the enablers that are detailed in D2.1 whose main target is the design and development of algorithms and APIs that dynamically optimise the service management in CAM roaming and cross-border scenarios. The data-driven (that is, AI/ML) algorithms will proactively migrate and dynamically place the CAM service functions at Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes.

In the context of the 5G-ROUTES project [20], these technological enablers are within the scope of Innovation Stream 2 (distributed MEC for Vehicle-to-everything (V2X)) and Innovation Stream 3 (cross-domain integration fabric) and will accomplish Objective 3 from the GA, namely, to advance and optimise the enabling technologies using AI for the reliable, seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable CAM services across borders.

7.1.1 Integration Fabric

The integration fabric will be implemented as a set of APIs, aimed at allowing the real-time exchange of data and analytics across borders and mobile network operators (MNO)s. This exchange of data and analytics has the final goal to facilitate the seamless CAM service delivery and roaming. The aforementioned APIs will be defined following the ETSI ZSM specifications [1] and exposed to the system using Open APIs tools such as AsyncAPI^{xxvi} and OpenAPI^{xxvii}. In the framework of 5G-ROUTES, the integration fabric will be used to coordinate the delivery of CAM services between neighbouring MNOs together with a CAM repository, which is aligned with the ETSI ZSM [1].

More specifically, the integration fabric will work as a shared message exchanging framework allowing interaction between the different components of an enabler as well as their interactions with others for “Day 1” and “Day 2” operations. These operations are aimed at initial configuration and re-configuration of the service when its behavior needs to be modified and can scale or run other closed-loop operations over it. The goal is to facilitate unified and automated service management in multi-domain and multi-MNO scenarios. In particular, the integration fabric will allow seamless cross-border service delivery, where individual virtual network function (VNF)s or microservices of the same CAM service can exchange state and engage in cross-domain coordination.

The integration fabric is a module in the 5G-ROUTES Platform Core Cloud that needs to be deployed at each MNO for coordinated management and support of CAM services.

7.1.1.1 Artefacts

The set of APIs will be implemented as Python scripts, running in the OSS. Whereas the communication with the other country domain will be implemented through Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) messages. One MQTT broker will be deployed at each domain. The MQTT brokers will be bridged, so that messages can be transmitted across domains. Containerized Linux OS will be used for the development process. Clarity on SW and HW requirements for the enabler in Day1 and Day2 operations will become clearer in the next phase, along the project progress.

7.1.1.2 Enabler Interfaces

Below is depicted the way that the Integration Fabric achieves communication across borders between neighboring MNOs, in order to ensure cross domain coordination. The integration fabric will follow the pub/sub pattern, leveraging on MQTT brokers at each domain (black solid arrows) linked with a cross-domain event bus or MQTT bridging configuration^{xxviii} (green solid arrows). Thus, management services can publish information related to management data, network state, or changes to mobility patterns. Additional Web APIs for RESTful applications will be exposed as part of the enabler (black dotted lines) as to fully describe the interactions inside the 5G-ROUTES Platform.

Figure 22 Integration Fabric interfaces

7.1.1.3 Development Timeline

The whole enabler will be developed according to the methodologies explained in this deliverable. However, the first releasable version is planned to contain a limited set of functionalities as to facilitate the development of other enablers and then the final release will contain the remaining foreseen functionalities. Its progress in terms of development and integration will be provided in upcoming deliverables.

Table 6 Integration Fabric Task Activities Planning

Task Activities		Deadline
1	Initial deployment and configuration	M20
2	Final release of the enabler	M30

7.1.2 CAM Repository

5G-ROUTES aims at delivering UCs in multi-domain experiments where parts of a UC 5G deployment is transferred from one MNO domain to another as the user moves. This setup necessarily requires that the networks and VNF (CAM Services) of the UCs are known by the two MNOs in order to facilitate the service continuity and handover across border.

As part of the 5G-ROUTES Core Cloud, the CAM Repository will make it possible for UCs to upload their artefacts (NFV descriptors, docker images etc) in a single action to the 5G-ROUTES Platform instead of manually provisioning the infrastructure. Then, the CAM Repository will provision the corresponding 5G Orchestrators (NFVO) and virtualized infrastructures (VIMs) with the required resources to ensure that the UC can run in that environment. Since 5G-ROUTES proposes an architecture fully distributed per domain, meaning that each domain has a full-fledge 5G-ROUTES platform, the CAM Repository will make use of the cross-domain Integration Fabric to synchronize the artefacts that are uploaded to it between the neighboring instances of this enabler.

7.1.2.1 Artefacts

The CAM Repository will be built as a collection of loosely coupled microservices using Python, docker and Kubernetes. The exact resources required by the docker images are not yet clear, but it is not expected to pose any high restriction over the host that will instantiate it.

7.1.2.2 Enabler Interfaces

The CAM Repository is envisioned to take part of the onboarding of resources across MNOs during UC registration and onboarding to the 5G-ROUTES Platform. UCs will interact with the CAM Repository via the Tenant Web Portal (see Figure 23), which will connect a simple UI (form view) to the API offered by the CAM Repository through the Integration Fabric, allowing them to onboard artefacts of CAM Services. Then, it will interact with the corresponding NFVOs and VIMs to provision the different environments where the UC may run with the required resources. Lastly, The Integration Fabric offers a way for the neighboring instances of the CAM Repository to synchronize their inventory of artefacts as soon as a new package is provided.

Figure 23 CAM Repository interfaces

7.1.2.3 Development Timeline

The CAM Repository enabler is following the CI/CD methodology explained in this deliverable and therefore incremental updates of it will be made available and tested against the CTTC testbed. However, a tentative schedule of main releases is considered and presented in Table 7.

Table 7 CAM Repository Task Activities Planning

Task Activities		Deadline
1	Design and definition of functionalities	M12
2	Initial deployment in CTTC	M20
3	Final version for trials	M24
4	Improved version based on D4.3 and D4.6 outcome	M32

7.1.3 Assisted Handover in Cross-domain

The main task of this enabler is to assist the handover in a cross-border environment so that the service that a driver is experiencing is affected the minimum in terms of interruption. An OBU in the car is equipped with different sensors such as, lidar, NFC, GPS and a camera. The OBU is exchanging MQTT messages with a MEC server. Depending on the location of the vehicle or on the strength of the mobile signal, the OBU is instructed to get an IP address to the network that is most reliable to continue the services to the vehicle.

This enabler will be offered to UCs as part of the Edge Cloud of the 5G-ROUTES Platform so that latency is reduced during consumption of the functionality.

7.1.3.1 Artefacts

This enabler has two sides in order to offer its functionality, it will provide a set of microservices based on Python at the Edge Cloud of the 5G-ROUTES Platform, which will be dockerized. Then, the UC side will require to add a script, also based on Python, to the OBU so that client and server connect. The resources required by the docker images are not clear but will be minimum to run the enabler.

7.1.3.2 Enabler Interfaces

This enabler will leverage the communication fabric offered by the V2X Broker in order to communicate the client and server side of the enabler.

7.1.3.3 Development Timeline

Table 8 depicts the development timeline and planned main releases for the enabler.

Table 8 Assisted handover Task Activities Planning

Task Activities		Deadline
1	Development and testing of the algorithm internally	M18
2	Finalization of algorithm and upload to cloud	M21
3	Testing at CTTC lab	M22
4	Enabler to be tested in field trials	M33

7.1.4 Resource Allocation and Positioning of V2X relate NFs

This enabler will pre-emptively allocate the resources that will be needed for the optimal functioning of the V2X NFs. Additionally, it will ascertain the need of migration and proper positioning of V2X VNFs in the Edge Cloud and MEC network components. If the mechanism ascertains that cross-border migration is required, it can interoperate with either the Assisted Handover mechanism presented in Chapter 7.1.3 or, when dealing specifically with CAM services that require low latency, with the mechanism presented in Chapter 7.1.5. It is a centralized component deployed on the top of the infrastructure as part of the Core Cloud of the 5G-ROUTES Platform and will be tested in the CTTC testbed before used in a Use Case.

7.1.4.1 Artefacts

The final form of the enabler will be a docker image exposing a service, written in Python 3 and utilizing the Pytorch^{xxx} python Library. It will require at least 2 GB of free disk space and at least 4 GB of RAM. Software and hardware requirement for the enabler in Day1 and Day2 operation are not available yet.

7.1.4.2 Enabler Interfaces

The enabler needs interfaces to various other components to operate. More specifically the following interfaces are needed:

- Access to Integration Fabric for slice/VNF requirements
- Access V2X Routing for MEC enablers for Vehicle specific data
- Access to Network Slice Management Function (NSFM) APIs for resource allocation and positioning
- Access to Network Slice Subnet Management Function (NSSFM) APIs for resource allocation and positioning
- Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM) for current resource use related information

7.1.4.3 Development Timeline

The following Chapter contains, in Table 9, a tentative schedule for the development and testing of the resource allocation and positioning of V2X related NFs enabler.

Table 9: Resource allocation and positioning of V2X related NFs enabler Task Activities Planning

Task Activities		Deadline
1	Initial Algorithm Development and Implementation	M19
2	First Release to be testing at CTTC lab	M20
3	Lab Testing / Simulations	M22
4	Performance Evaluation	M24
5	Second release	M24
6	Final Version	M30

7.1.5 Low-latency Cross-border Synchronisation Mechanism for Seamless CAM Service Delivery

The synchronization mechanism will provide seamless cross-border CAM delivery, by following a hot standby strategy, a full state synchronization of the primary and standby CAM services. To achieve cross-border functionality two criteria need to be provided by the infrastructure:

- A communication channel between the 2 MNOs, the role of which will fulfil the multi-domain/multi-MNO interfaces provided in 5G-ROUTES.
- SLAs and NFV descriptors mapped to the appropriate MNO, to ensure that the CAM service can run in each domain.

The 5G-ROUTES infrastructure fulfils both points: the first one is addressed by the integration fabric and the mapping between descriptors and MNOs by the Slice Negotiator and the CAM repository.

The mechanism will be a centralized component as part of the 5G-ROUTES Platform Core Cloud, in order to be able to manage cross-border requests for a synchronization link's updates and provide easier cross VNF synchronization dependencies, as well as better network monitoring services. Each CAM service will be able to utilize the synchronization link by making use of the enabler's exposed services in the form of two interfaces, one to request the service and another one to receive the transferred information from the neighbour domain.

The enabler will allow:

1. Initialization of the synchronization link by connecting the two VNFs. In this step the basic identification credentials in the synchronization service are transmitted, as well as if the CAM service will be uploading or downloading its state.

2. Setup of a data link between the synchronization manager VNF and the service, through the port specified in the network service descriptor. The data link will allow the following actions:
 - Initialize Synchronization: where the current extracted state of the initial CAM service is transferred to the synchronization manager and transmitted to the target CAM service.
 - UpdateState: where the delta changes from the previous synchronizations is propagated to the synchronization manager and to the target CAM service.
 - Terminate synchronization link: when the synchronization has been finalized.
3. Termination of the synchronization link and clean up.

The state propagation will be realized by a push approach via the CAM service's interface. The footprint of the enabler in the 5G-ROUTES Platform and CAM Services will vary depending on the target network and availability KPIs, as well as if the application's state can be extracted and stored. For services where the state can be extracted the impact of the enabler is minimal and requires a state push to the synchronization manager, in case a service is stateful, then it will be application specific. The enabler will be tested in the TTU testbed, before being utilized for the UC.

7.1.5.1 Artefacts

The enabler will be delivered as a VNF, containing the synchronization manager, and will be accompanied by another VNF consisting of a synchronization client that will be performing synchronization of a file system. The synchronization client will be able to be used with any CAM Service that is able to extract and store its state on the filesystem. The main language used will be C++.

The technical requirements are:

- at least 4 GB of RAM.
- 2 GB of free disk space, without taking into consideration the size of the transferred state itself.
- A GNU/Linux OS distribution, preferably Ubuntu 18.04 LTS or 16.04 LTS.

Software and hardware requirement for the enabler in Day1 and Day2 operation are not available yet.

7.1.5.2 Enabler Interfaces

The enabler needs interfaces to various other components to operate (see Figure 24). More specifically the following interfaces are needed:

- Access to CSMF Slice Negotiator APIs for slice/VNF requirements.
- Access to NSFM APIs to create the communication streams between the CAM services by using functionalities of the NSSFM and in order to provide network monitoring information.
- Access to NSSFM APIs, in order to create new network sub-slices for the synchronization streams.

The enabler will provide two interfaces for other CAM services; however, in order to fulfill state synchronization for various scenarios a synchronization observer API will be provided as well as a synchronization observer implementation for completely stateless scenarios (e.g. where the state is extracted and stored in disk). The following interfaces will be provided:

- A "Synchronization Request Manager" that will receive requests by the other CAM services by providing as input a handle to the state observer API implementation. As output a synchronization handle will be created.
- A "Synchronization Handle" which will control the synchronization rate, as well as the ability to terminate the synchronization process when the handover is complete.

Figure 24 Low-latency cross-border Synchronization for CAM Services Enabler

7.1.5.3 Development Timeline

The following Section contains, in Table 10, a schedule for the development and testing of the Low-latency cross-border synchronization for CAM services enabler.

Table 10 Low-latency cross-border synchronisation mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery task activity planning

Task Activities		Deadline
1	Initial Algorithm Development and Implementation	M19
2	First Release to be testing at TTU lab	M20
3	First release to be implemented in trial site.	M22
4	Second version will be available.	M24
5	Lab testing and performance evaluation	M25
6	Final Version	M31

7.1.6 V2X Routing using MEC

The enabler is part of the Edge Cloud of the 5G-ROUTES Platform and is planned to support the communication architecture between vehicles which is depicted Figure 25. The following actors involved in the architecture can be defined:

- Vehicles.
- Service provider. The service provider can make use of edge computing to put applications closer to the vehicle. Hence, the information path may be either direct to the application back office (ITS center back office) or through the MEC.

The V2X MQTT-AMQP-based routing application will be deployed on the MEC. The application will be used by the V2X use cases, with a major impact on UC1.3, UC2.1, UC2.2 and UC3.3.

The routing application will be tested in the VTT testbed as part of the lab trials for UC3.1 and UC3.3.

7.1.6.1 Artefacts

The plan is to deploy the application as a docker. The memory size will be determined later. The amount of storage is also affected by the amount of logging required to support evaluation in the 5G-ROUTES project.

7.1.6.2 Enabler Interfaces

The application works as MQTT broker, communicating with clients in the vehicle. The exact protocol and version for the exchange of information with other servers is being decided so that it easily integrates with the WP2 and WP3 dev teams.

The following protocols are identified at this point (see Figure 25):

- V2BO: Vehicle to Back office, used for communication with individual vehicles.
- V2MEC: Vehicle to MEC
- MEC2BO: for communication between vehicles. This protocol will also be used for communications between two different MECs.
- BO2BO: communication between back offices.

Figure 25 V2X communication architecture using MQTT/AMQP – based routing application

The interface specifications will be determined with the partners involved in the other use cases during the WP3 work.

7.1.6.3 Development Timeline

The first release of the application is planned to be ready for the first set of trials, and will contain a minimum set of functionalities, at least brokerage of MQTT messages and message exchange to other MECs. The first release will be tested during the first series of lab trials in Autumn 2021 and made available for the first series of large-scale trials at the end of 2021. The performance will be tested during the lab trials.

The second version will include geolocation support and will be tested during the second series of lab trials in Spring 2022 and made available for the large-scale trials in Mid-2022. See Table 11 for a tentative schedule for the development and testing of V2X routing using MEC.

Table 11 V2X routing using MEC Task Activities Planning

Task Activities		Deadline
1	First version with connection to other MECs	M13
2	Lab testing and performance evaluation	M14
3	First release to be implemented in trial site	M20
4	Second version with geolocation	M24
5	Lab testing and performance evaluation	M27
6	Final release to be implemented in trial site	M30

7.2 End-to-End Slicing Optimization and Innovative Spectrum Usage for CAM Services

This Chapter covers the enablers that are detailed in D2.3 which main target is to define and implement an E2E slicing framework, supporting enhanced resource and spectrum allocation capabilities, with different granularities, from coarse-grained high-level application requirements and operator Service Level Agreements (SLA) to fine-grained 5G radio interface slicing.

The enablers detailed in this Chapter contribute to satisfy Objective 3 of the 5G-ROUTES GA by targeting the use of AI for the delivery of CAM services across borders. The enablers are also aligned with innovation Stream 1 by utilising AI based network slicing to achieve service continuity across borders and innovation Stream 5 for achieving positioning enhancements by using AI.

7.2.1 Network Slicing for CAM Services

The envisioned network slicing solution is aimed at optimizing the available network resources while meeting the SLAs of the CAM services. This is achieved through two mechanisms:

1. Predicting future availability of network resources / capacity needs of existing CAM services based on current network state, vehicular metrics and historical data as well as considering CAM SLAs. CAM service requests received from the CSMF, the data about network state originates from the RAN and Core, historical data from centralized AI/ML module or stored locally in each network element, the vehicle traffic related data is collected by the TMS.
2. Dynamic resource (re)allocation based on the CAM service (originated in the MNO network or in the neighboring MNOs) needs, current and forecasted system state.

7.2.1.1 Artefacts

Python is the preferred programming language, and the tentative plan is to offer the technological enabler as an ML model. The DL model is currently developed in TensorFlow but PyTorch is also commonly used and is not excluded as an option for any future developments. Other possible DRL tools are OpenAI^{xxx} Gym or RISELab UC Berkeley^{xxxi}.

Memory and storage requirements will be available upon model completion but typically these are in the order of GB. Linux OS is currently used for the development process. Clarity on SW and HW requirements for the enabler in Day1 and Day2 operations will become clearer in the next phase as the project progresses.

7.2.1.2 Enabler Interfaces

The Network Slicing for CAM enabler will communicate with the CSMF (Communication Service Management Function) and NSSMF (Network Slice Sub-net Management Function). The interfaces description to be further refined upon architecture definition.

7.2.1.3 Development Timeline

The first version of the prediction algorithm (temporal but no spatial considerations) is planned to be ready for the first quarter (Q1) of 2022 (see Table 12). Subject to the availability of LMT and Telia data, it will be next evaluated with real data from highways. The second version of the algorithm will account for the spatial correlations of vehicular traffic and mobility and is planned to be ready by Q2 of 2022. The development work on the dynamic resource allocation is planned to commence concurrently with the latest phase of the prediction model in Q2 2022 and its development to be finalised by the end of last quarter, Q4, of 2022 / beginning of Q1 2022 along with its performance evaluation.

The network slicing solution will be integrated and tested in the CTTC testbed during Q2 of 2022. It will be also offered by the UCs that could benefit of it as indicated in D2.3.

Table 12 Network slicing for CAM solution: development plan

Task Activities		Deadline
MS1	Prediction algorithm: design, implementation and evaluation (v1)	M22
MS2	First release (v1) to be integrated in CTTC testbed	M25
MS3	Optimisation algorithm: design, implementation and evaluation (v1)	M29
MS4	Final release of the algorithms	M33
MS5	Integration in CTTC testbed, testing and performance results	M34

7.2.2 Slice Negotiator

The Slice negotiator enabler in the 5G-ROUTES Platform Core Cloud covering parts of the CSMF functionalities. It is fully detailed in D2.3 as part of the T2.2 of the WP2. The Slice Negotiator has two main responsibilities:

1. To receive network slice requests from the vertical (e.g. through the portal) and translate these requests into network slice templates (e.g. NEST templates) and further forward the templates to the NSMF for the realization of the network slices;
2. At a cross border depending on the use case a slice request is initiated and then the resources at the cross border are negotiated. To negotiate with other instances the Slice Negotiator will receive the slice request from the TWP and then negotiates at the cross border different MNOs/countries the appropriate creation of the appropriate network slice with the proper resources for the other MNO/country.

7.2.2.1 Artefacts

Slice Negotiator will be provided as VNF. It will be developed in Java and will interact with the Tenant Web Portal through the Integration Fabric and with external entities through REST APIs/JSON.

7.2.2.2 Enabler Interfaces

This enabler will interact with the rest of the 5G-ROUTES Platform using the Integration Fabric and with any external component using their APIs and protocols. This includes:

- North Bound interface toward Verticals (e.g. Portal).
- South Bound interface toward NSMF
- East/West Bound interfaces toward others Slice Negotiator instances

7.2.2.3 Development Timeline

See Table 13 for a tentative schedule for the development and testing of the slice negotiator.

Table 13 Slice negotiator Task Activities Planning

Task Activities		Deadline
1	Development of the slice negotiation component (including slice negotiation algorithm, translation process and required interfaces) in WINGS premises.	M19
2	Test the slice negotiation component in the lab.	M20
3	Finalization of slice negotiation component and upload to repository as VNF.	M20
4	Testing at CTTC lab	M20
5	Final version of the enabler	M30

7.3 AI-based Positioning Enhancements for V2X

Contributions to this Chapter of the deliverable corresponds to T2.3 “AI-based positioning enhancements” and associated D2.5 “AI-based positioning enhancements for V2X v1.0” which will be later complemented with D2.6 “AI-based positioning enhancements for V2X v2.0”.

7.3.1 5G Localization for VRU Protection

The 5G Localization enabler is an edge enabler that will perform track-level fusion using the low-level fused data from the RSUs, the vehicle OBUs and other actors that are interconnected in a ETSI defined collective perception system. The system will depend on the V2X Routing enabler for the participation in the CPS system, by subscribing to the appropriate MQTT topics. Figure 26 shows the closed loop control system that fuses the different VRU perceptions. In this figure several message abbreviations are used:

- Cooperative Awareness Message (CAM).
- Collective Perception Message (CPM)
- Decentralized Environmental Notification Message (DENM)

The closed loop consists of:

- Decoding the received messages of the latest time slot.
- Clustering of the input data.
- Data association to the current state’s VRUs.
- Predicting the next position by utilizing VRUs perceived kinematic data.
- Update of all the VRUs state.
- Forming, encoding and broadcasting the newly created CPM by MQTT publishing to the appropriate topic.

The enabler will be tested in the TTU testbed, before being utilized for the UC.

Figure 26 VRU Localization Closed Loop

7.3.1.1 Artefacts

The final form of the enabler will be a docker image hosting the localization service and the programming language of choice is not defined but will most likely be C++. The service will require at least 4 GB of free disk space and at least 4 GB of RAM on a GNU/LINUX based operating system. The amount of ram and disk space will need to scale based on the amount of the actors that need to be tracked, however the predicted amount is enough for the current scenarios. More accurate values will be provided once the results of the simulations are available. Software and hardware requirements for the enabler in Day1 and Day2 operation are not available yet.

7.3.1.2 Enabler Interfaces

The enabler depends on the V2X Routing for MEC enabler and follows the MQTT publish/subscribe model. The interface (see Figure 27) specification will be determined with the WP3 partners as this enabler is closely related to UC 3.3. Moreover, to acquire cross border functionality, the enabler will make use of the infrastructure provided by the assisted handover enabler, as well as the Low-latency cross-border synchronization mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery by adopting the enabler’s interface.

Figure 27 VRU Localization interfaces

7.3.1.3 Development Timeline

See Table 14 for a tentative development and testing for 5G localization for VRU protection.

Table 14 5G localization for VRU protection enabler Task Activities Planning

Task Activities		Deadline
1	Initial Algorithm Development and Implementation	M19
2	First Release to be testing at TTU lab	M20
3	First release to be implemented in trial site.	M22
4	Second version will be available.	M24
5	Lab testing and performance evaluation	M25
6	Final Version	M31

7.3.2 5G Network-based Positioning and 5G Integrated Hybrid Positioning

The 5G positioning enabler is built upon Ericsson network location (ENL) product and its integration with 5G SA core network. There are a number of advanced mobile positioning methods which ENL will provide, and 5G-ROUTES trials will be early adapter of these advanced positioning. Details of the ENL product are provided in D2.5. The main goal of the enabler is to first test and evaluate the performance of the ENL 5G solutions, collect data from 5G NSA and 5G SA network and then further enhance and optimize the positioning performed by means of i) the advanced and enhanced cell-id (AECID) Fingerprinting supported by ENL product for mMTC use-cases and ii) GNSS-RTK 5G integrated hybrid solution to provide for C-CAM V2X use-cases. The AECID method takes for input radio measurements data such as RSSI, RSRP, RSRQ, etc. to generate the baseline localization results (map database); however, the accuracy that can be achieved is of the tens of meters order could be meeting the requirements of mMTC use-cases (UC3.2, UC5.1, UC5.2). The enabler will be tested in TTU testbed described in Chapter 6.3.2 and D2.5. This enabler can be deployed at any time. It can be duplicated, assuming the partner has access to the same infrastructure.

7.3.2.1 Artefacts

- Localization algorithms developed in D2.5 and further enhanced through ML classification in D2.6, which will be integrated within this enabler.

- The enabler will take the form of a Docker image exposing an enhanced localization data. It will be written in Python 3 and utilizing the Pytorch python Library. It will require at least 2 GB of free disk space and at least 4 GB of RAM. Software and hardware requirement for the enabler in Day1 and Day2 operation are not available yet.

7.3.2.2 Enabler Interfaces

As can be seen in Figure 28, the enabler is connected to the 5G SA network via a 5G Network Exposure Function (NEF). Also, in order to improve the baseline results, the enabler exploits additional measurements data from GPS and RTK. These data feed ML-based algorithms (“LOS/NLOS” and “user segregation based on the QoS”) to enhance accuracy.

Figure 28. Approach for improving localization accuracy.

The inputs of the enablers are:

1. The results (map) of the AECID localization performed in the network
2. GPS measurements data
3. RTK measurements data

The output of the enabler is:

1. The improved accuracy localization map exposed to UC through the V2X Routing enabler

7.3.2.3 Development Timeline

Although it is still in an early stage of planning, the first tentative development schedule is presented in Table 15

Table 15 5G network-based positioning and 5G integrated hybrid positioning task activities planning

Task Activities		Deadline
1	1. 5G NSA/SA TN Measurements to collect network and GPS data to develop maps for fingerprinting i) 5G integrated GNSS-RTK data collection and device integration	M22
2	Field trials with RTK and complementary AI/ML based fingerprinting algorithm based on MLP and DL at the UC site with WP3 partners	M25
3	Training of ML models for the enabler based on collected data	M26
4	First version of enabler to be integrated in the testbed	M26
5	Lab Testing / integration with ENL	M30
6	Performance Evaluation	M32
7	Final Version ready for the field trials	M35
8	Final D2.6 ready	M35

7.4 Tenant Web Portal

In alignment and with relevance to the overall project, and the approach followed to achieve the objectives, the Tenant Web Portal (TWP) is a web-based solution which will be the main User Interface (UI) and a visualisation environment for the UC owners to setup information about their UCs, and scenarios but also to enable the monitoring and real-time graph data presentation, of the experiment's execution. More information about the TWP can be found in D2.7 "Tenant Web Portal implementation and deployment (V1)".

The TWP can be considered as part of the 5G-ROUTES Platform Core Cloud since it will be placed in the infrastructure of the testbeds and communicate with every CAM Service.

The TWP employs numerous modules/mechanisms to process the information ingested from the lab or field trials during the experimentation of the different UCs and makes it available through the Web. The use of the TWP is considered as an important element to 5G-ROUTES to automate and accelerate the execution of the use cases running in parallel, as well as the analysis, benchmarking, and presentation of the technical KPIs from cross-border field trials, whilst being in the field, by using big-data graph analytics and cloud-computing for rapid and automated processing of the vast amount of data obtained from the trials. TWP components are listed below and further analyzed in D2.7:

1. **Data Collector:** Automates and accelerates the execution of the use cases running in parallel and handles the processing of the vast amount of data. It is responsible for the integration with the UCs where data are collected (via the 5G nodes). It also handles the integration with the rest enablers via secured MQTT.
2. **Data Processor:** Performs near real-time processing on the collected data. By processing we mean the homogenisation of data, anonymisation (whenever needed) and their transformation to predefined KPIs, corresponding to trials of different use case scenarios. Finally, is responsible to store the data in the TWP database.
3. **Data storage (database):** The TWP database where information on the tests performed, raw test data collected and the KPIs are stored. This database is part of the TWP and is planned to be deployed along with the rest components, on each test side.

4. **User Interface:** While data are captured and uploaded or imported, TWP provides different type of user interface in the concept of “dashboards”, where information about experiments, raw test data and calculated KPIs can be visualized. It also provides an additional functionality like setup and modify UCs, scenarios and Performance Indicators, setup the UCs execution (start/stop a trial), logging of trial execution.

The diagram in Figure 29 provides a deeper visual into the components of the TWP, the data flow and how those are interacted between them. In the left side, we see that lab or field trials input data will be ingested into the secured Core Cloud environment of 5G-ROUTES, received by the Data Collector, and passing then to the Data Processor where are stored in the secured cloud database. As a final step, the defined KPIs are calculated and presented in the User Interface (accessing data from the database via the Data Processor) where the UC owners have access via a secure https browser access.

Figure 29 TWP Visualization Dashboard Components and Flow of Information

The TWP implementation includes the creation of the necessary packages for the container-based deployment of the TWP, as a service in the cloud. This will eventually enable the easy setup, configuration, and micro-service-oriented deployment of the Portal in the lab trials (to ensure proper operation, concept verification and usability testing prior to field trials) but also the concurrent UC execution to quickly match specific field trials configurations.

7.4.1 Artefacts

For the implementation of the main UI where KPIs are presented, Grafana⁵ has been selected. The following are the software, hardware and technical requirements related to the Tenant Portal:

- **Supported operating systems:** The following operating systems are supported for TWP installation: Debian / Ubuntu, RPM-based Linux (CentOS, Fedora, OpenSuse, RedHat), Windows.
- **Hardware specifications:** The TWP does not use many resources; it is very lightweight in use of memory and CPU and usually loads dashboards within 10-500 ms. The minimum recommended memory is 255 MB while the minimum recommended CPU is 1.
- **Supported databases:** The TWP requires a database to store trials data and implemented dashboards. Tenant Portal supports database like Microsoft SQL Server, SQLite, MySQL and PostgreSQL.

⁵ <https://grafana.com/>

- **Supported web browsers:** TWP is supported in the current version of the following browsers: Chrome, Firefox, Safari, Microsoft Edge, Internet Explorer 11. Older versions of these browsers might not be supported, so one should always upgrade to the latest version when using Tenant Portal.

7.4.2 Tenant Web Portal Interfaces

For the TWP to be validated, there is a high dependency on the Integration Fabric (IF) endpoints, messages format and the definition of the KPIs. For the use case specific tests, data can be collected by the TWP on real-time, through a client MQTT which subscribes to the data collection topics for intra-domain and inter-domain messages in the Integration Fabric. The idea is that the UCs do communicate with the IF broker directly to push metrics to the TWP database. They will have network connectivity at the Edge since the enablers that are deployed there will be configured to share the same network with those that are deployed at the core cloud of the 5G-ROUTES Platform (they also need to have access to the IF to communicate with other enablers and store their own metrics).

TPW also provides a data download functionality where UC leaders can download the data collected or historical data. An additional REST API could also be exposed by the TWP to serve the need of provision historical data.

7.4.3 Development Timeline

Based on the implementation plan, a three -phases implementation process has been followed, having in mind the requirements-design-continues development approach. This is presented Table 16 with the involvement of EBOS (as Task Leader) and WINGS, ATOS, ENIDE (as Task Contributors). More information about the implementation phases and task activities are presented in D2.7.

- Phase 1: Requirement’s Collection and Designs
- Phase 2: Wireframes and Mock-up Designs
- Phase 3: Development

Table 16 Tenant Web Portal Development Timeline

	Task Activities	Deadline
1.Requirement’s Collection and Designs	Collect of requirements and define the technology to be used	M6
2.Wireframes and Mock-up Designs	Create a low-lever design, wireframes and TWP mock-up screens	M10
3.Development	Development of TWP prototype version	M15
	Development of TWP intermediate version and deployment	M19
	Development of TWP final version and deployment	M29

8 5G-ROUTES Platform

The present Chapter builds on top of the knowledge gained until M16 of the 5G-ROUTES project and elaborates an aggregated system considering all of the enablers developed in WP2. The 5G-ROUTES Platform is a multi-cloud system (core and edge) built as the combination of innovative technological enablers developed within the project to comply with the needs of CAM UCs. By correctly integrating and deploying the enablers according to their needs and interfaces (Chapter 7) and the guidelines of this deliverable (Chapter 4, 5, 6), WP2 will be able to deliver a 5G-ROUTES Platform to successive WPs and UCs. A successful deployment of enablers shall be able to offer a gateway for UCs to execute experiments in a 5G network either within a testbed or field trial.

The list of enablers that compose the 5G-ROUTES Platform has been aligned with the needs of the specific UCs of the 5G-ROUTES project. In result, the integration of said Platform in the MNO’s infrastructure during field trials will be able to provide customized functionalities to the different UCs that shall run experiments in their domain without the need of additional parametrization of the Platform when changing from one UC and another. The objective is to have the enablers integrated and deployed at all times and allow UCs to quickly leverage functionalities of enablers of their own choice. Table 17 depicts the current mapping between enablers and UCs elaborated through several workshops and combined WP2 and WP3 meetings. Those cells marked with an A in Table 17 mean that the enabler is Applicable to the corresponding UC, this is the case of most core enablers, since they participate in the onboarding and instantiation steps. Cells marked as Not Relevant refer to those cases in which the functionalities of the enabler seem to not be required by the UC at this point although they may be able to use them if proved beneficial. Finally, since discussions are still ongoing, some enablers are marked as To Be Determined (TBD), indicating that the final decision of whether it will be used or not will be reported in upcoming deliverables.

Table 17 Enablers mapping to UCs in 5G-ROUTES

Enabler	UC1.1	UC1.2	UC1.3	UC2.1	UC2.2	UC3.1	UC3.2	UC3.3	UC4.1	UC4.2	UC5.1	UC5.2	UC5.3
Integration Fabric	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Network Slicing for CAM Services	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
CAM Repository	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Slice Negotiator	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Resource allocation and positioning of V2X related NFs	A	A	TBD	A	A	A	TBD	A	A	A	Not relevant	Not relevant	Not relevant
Tenant web portal	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
Assisted handover	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	TBD	A
Low-latency cross-border synchronisation mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery	A	A	TBD	A	A	TBD	Not relevant	A	A	Not relevant	Not relevant	TBD	Not relevant
V2X routing using MEC	A	A	A	A	A	A	Not relevant	A	Not relevant	Not relevant	Not relevant	TBD	TBD
5G localization for VRU protection	Not relevant	Not relevant	Not relevant	A	A	A	Not relevant	A	Not relevant				
5G network-based positioning and 5G integrated hybrid positioning	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	Not relevant	A	A	TBD

T2.5 will oversee that the acceptance criteria of the CICD pipeline implemented for the 5G-ROUTES Platform (see Section 5.3) is, at least, able to prove that enablers can be deployed through a 5G Orchestrator (OSM will be used in testbeds according to Section 6.3) in a way that enablers have network connectivity considering a multi-cloud deployment.

Taking the original architecture diagram presented in D2.1 (see Figure 16), T2.5 has gone inside each block of the diagram that contains enablers and placing the final selection according to Chapter 7 where they belong. 5G-ROUTES Platform (see Figure 30) is initially designed according to the available 5G infrastructure of the project’s testbeds but considers the possible differences with the field trials infrastructure to reduce risks and compatibility issues. Although T2.5 will ensure that the 5G-ROUTES Platform is functional at the testbed level, parallel tasks from WP3 are working on the field trials setup and will continue to provide feedback on what is

discovered so that the testbed setup is as similar as possible to the commercial infrastructure deployed for the field trials.

Figure 30 5G-ROUTES Platform overview

Figure 30 shows that at least two communication protocols will be used to exchange information between enablers (inside Core and Edge 5G-ROUTES clouds), UCs and the 5G Infrastructure.

1. Dotted lines correspond to a REST interface. These APIs will be mainly used for the interaction between the enablers and the 5G infrastructure. In favour of extensibility and openness, all new APIs created by the TWP and enablers will follow the OpenAPIs specification. This will ease integration among the enablers and extension of functionalities.
2. Solid lines conform the platform's event driven communication framework which will be used to converge most of the internal traffic of the Platform via the Integration Fabric and the V2X enabler. In the interest of aligning with the previous case, APIs will follow the AsyncAPI specification to fully define what services are exposed and consumed by the enablers of the Platform as well as those being made available for UCs. Its main use will be to host enabler-to-enabler communications for both, intra-domain and cross-domain interactions.

8.1 Core Cloud Enablers

Information collected in Chapter 7 allow us to zoom in the 5G-ROUTES cloud boxes from Figure 30. Within the Core cloud of the Platform, the set of enablers depicted in Figure 31 correspond to those categorized as Core enablers in Table 5.

Figure 31 5G-ROUTES Core Cloud

It is worth mentioning that the Integration Fabric is used by most of the interactions among enablers in an asynchronous way although other communications will require a different approach depending on the component to which the enabler interacts outside the 5G-ROUTES Platform. Looking at the caption of arrows in the top left corner of Figure 31, it is shown that solid black arrows denote interactions that use the intra-domain Integration Fabric MQTT bus, while those in green indicate that will use the cross-domain Integration Fabric MQTT bus to reach other instances of the same enabler at the neighbour deployment of the 5G-ROUTES Platform. Additional dotted lines have been added to illustrate which enabler will be using the interface offered by the 5G Orchestrator of the domain where they are operating to offer their services.

Other than enablers, Figure 31 shows an additional component that was not previously identified, a AI/ML Server. Due to the AI/ML capabilities of most enablers, it is proposed to centralize the execution of resource-demanding algorithms in a dedicated microservice. An AI/ML Server such as Tensorflow Serving^{xxii} offers a very simple and straightforward way to upload AI/ML models to it and request their execution via a REST API at any time, it will additionally help to reduce the complexity and fingerprint of the enablers. These communications are shown as dotted lines in Figure 31.

Another resource that is used by many enablers is the Data Collector gateway (shown as a database in Figure 31) to a database managed by the Tenant Web Portal which is reachable by all enablers and UCs via the Integration Fabric. That way they will be able to push metrics and other relevant information through the Integration Fabric to be collected and saved in a backend database. Historical data will be accessible at the TWP dashboard to visualize and download. This approach will help minimize the difficult debugging and maintainability that comes from systems in which storage is self-contained in every microservice. More information on this topic is available in D2.7 and D1.5.

8.2 Edge Cloud Enablers

In an additional effort to leverage the improved performance of services that can be achieved by the capability of 5G to deploy Network Services (NS) closer to the users, 5G-ROUTES will be offering UC-oriented enablers deployed at the Edge/MEC in favours of a low latency delivery of functionalities.

Figure 32 5G-ROUTES Edge Cloud

Enablers shown in Figure 32 correspond to those that were classified as Edge enablers in Table 5. Similar to Figure 31, solid lines are used to denote MQTT-based communications. In this case, two new buses are offered by the V2X Routing enabler to provide the services that were explained in Chapter 7.1.6.

Figure 32 includes a direct link for UCs to store their required metrics to the Tenant Web Portal in the Core Cloud. In fact, green is used to denote what was originally defined in D2.7 about the synchronization mechanisms of the TWP databases at both domains through the Integration Fabric’s cross-domain bus.

These enablers are closely linked to the UCs being developed in WP3 since they offer very specific functionalities to the User Equipment and CAM Services of UCs. This relationship was previously shown in D2.1 and further justified in D3.3.

9 Conclusions

This report has compiled a set of guidelines, methodologies and tools that WP2 will endorse to drive the development and testing of the technological enablers and the 5G-ROUTES Platforms at the initial stages of the project. The methodologies evaluated facilitate a CICD approach that will empower developers to produce a set of validated and trusted enablers so that they can be integrated in the 5G-ROUTES Platform with high reliability and thus, ascertain the 5G technology and its exploitation to achieve novel CAM Services.

The report has elaborated the specific requirements for the deployment of the components in the different testbeds that will evaluate the functionalities of the enablers. Enablers are expected to provide some level of testing at the laboratories at early stages in one of those offered by the consortium, namely, CTTC Testbed in Barcelona, TTU Testbed located in Estonia, and VTT Testbed located in Tampere, Espoo and Oulu. The document also describes the cloud capabilities and access connectivity to perform the automated integration of the enablers in each one of these sites which is leveraged in the proposed integration and deployment strategy.

During the upcoming period, the mentioned development and integration methodology will result in the provisioning of the required code repositories in the 5G-ROUTES GitLab group, which will serve as the basis to validate in WP3 the several UC trials. The releases will evaluate the correctness of enablers, iterating over the development, and improving following releases towards the validation in the extended localized trials.

This document covers a first version of the testing and integration of enablers task of the project, it is focused on the specification and methodology proposed so that enabler can start to be developed under a common umbrella as well as the underlying virtualization technologies for deploying the 5G-ROUTES Platform in the testbed. The second version of this deliverable will describe in more detail the functionalities that will be tested together with the test description that will be performed in every laboratory site, prior to the validation of the different UCs. This iterative cycle will be repeated until the final versions of the proposed technological enablers are developed and delivered, which shall be described in D2.10 Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v2.0 at the end of this WP2 in M36.

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